

Testing and Verification for Computer Vision

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Contents

1	CNNs for Object Classification	3
1.1	Introduction	3
1.2	Deep Learning Algorithms	5
1.2.1	Non-Convolutional Neural Network	6
1.3	Convolutional Neural Networks.	7
1.3.1	Convolution	9
1.3.2	Activation Functions	11
1.3.3	Pooling	12
1.4	Object Detection	14
1.4.1	Region Proposals	17
1.5	R-CNN family	19
1.5.1	R-CNN	19
1.5.2	Fast R-CNN	22
1.5.3	Faster R-CNN	25
1.6	YOLO	29
1.6.1	Output Tensor	31
1.7	Object Detection in Videos	31
1.7.1	Rolling Averages approach	32
1.7.2	Late Fusion Architecture	33
1.7.3	Pool Late Fusion	34
1.7.4	Early Fusion Architecture	35
1.7.5	3D Convolutional Networks	36
1.8	Conclusion	37
2	Testing & Verification of Neural Networks	39
2.1	Introduction	39
2.2	Background	40
2.2.1	Abstraction of Neural Network	40
2.2.2	Defining Specifications	43
2.3	Constraint-Based Verification	45
2.3.1	Encoding Neural Networks	46
2.3.2	DPLL (Davis-Putnam-Logemann-Loveland)	53
2.3.3	Theory Solving	61
2.4	Abstraction Based Verification	66

2.4.1	Neural Interval Abstraction	68
2.4.2	Zonotope: Relational Abstract Domain	73
2.4.3	Neural Polyhedron Abstraction	78
2.4.4	Abstract Interpretation based Verification	81
2.4.5	Abstract Training of Neural Networks	84
2.5	Testing Neural Networks	88
2.5.1	Adversarial Testing	89
2.6	Conclusion	95

Chapter 1

CNNs for Object Classification

1.1 Introduction

Vision related tasks can be divided into two main classes: *Classification* and *Detection*. Classification is the identification of the particular class of an object in an example image given a set of k classes. Detection comprises of an additional task on top of the Classification wherein the position of classified object has to be identified. Thus, Detection entails the Classification and Localization of an object inside a given image where the object belongs to one of the predefined k object categories. Additionally, there are other variants of each of these tasks for single or multiple objects in the image. Although Classification problems as a paradigm are limited to a single object per image, they form the basis of *Image Segmentation*. Image Segmentation problems can be defined as the classification of different regions of an image, each to one of the given categories. Lastly we have *Multi-Object Detection* problems wherein multiple objects are identified and localized inn a given image.

Figure 1.1: Computer Vision problems at a glance [14]

These multiple classes of Classification and Detection problems are entirely intractable with traditional vision techniques. It is due to the advent of Deep Learning models and more specifically the many variants of the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) algorithm that progress has been made on these problems. Without Deep Learning algorithms, traditional hand-crafted algorithms did not have the prerequisite accuracy threshold to be adopted into production environments. Although previously utilized algorithmic methods reliably analysed visual data, they had high inductive biases and had correspondingly little flexibility in adapting to data shifts. That is to say that there was no consensus as to what invariant patterns could be used to analyse visual data and classify objects. This set of standards evolved with more and more complexity over time yet had subpar accuracy when compared to modern learning algorithms. More traditional techniques like filter banks, gradient clusters or edge detection utilize processing to extract data but there is a semantic gap between how we perceive images and how they are stored in the digital medium. Searching for points of interest or using matching descriptors are data dependent and rely heavy on preexisting image patches with poor generalization.

Figure 1.2: Image Recognition should be invariant to convolution and information loss [31]

A continuing thread in regards to computer vision tasks is the three invariants that should be accounted for in any algorithm aiming to successfully accomplish Image Classification tasks.

- Detecting Change in Gradients is important for detecting simple edges or blobs
- Simple features cascade to form a hierarchy of more and more complex features
- Information about spatial relations between objects should be preserved in order to retain their semantic meaning.

Therefore algorithms that account for these invariant properties are able to successfully perform image classification tasks. CNNs and its multiple variants have account for these elements in the structure of the algorithm itself and are therefore able to perform computer vision task with a high degree of accuracy. This report builds on the basic Convolutional Neural Network algorithm with its different iterations that are adapted for different tasks, along with a review of various algorithms for object tracking and detection in videos. There are various other manual methods of feature detection like HOG [4], SIFT [21] and other *Deformable Parts Models (DPMs)* [5] that have been omitted due to their diminished impact when dealing with computer vision tasks.

1.2 Deep Learning Algorithms

The success of different Deep Learning algorithms has been due to the expressiveness of *Neural Networks*.

Neural Networks are the technology underpinning the resurgence of Deep Learning algorithms. Neural Networks are just collections of nodes called *neurons* that are organized in a multitude of different *hidden* layers strung together

with the help of non-linearities called *activation functions*. These neurons although primarily inspired from the biological neuron serve very different functions. Each neuron acts as a linear classifier of the form

$$\hat{y} = \mathbf{W}^T \hat{x} + \mathbf{b}$$

where \hat{y} and \hat{x} are the output and input vectors for each neuron respectively and \mathbf{W}, \mathbf{b} are the weights and biases, collectively called the parameters of the neuron. If the neurons are part of the input layer, each element of the \hat{x} vector are the features that are ingested by the model in order to determine the class of the object.

Figure 1.3: Standard Neural Network with one hidden layer (3 nodes), two input nodes and one output node

Every neuron node computes an affine transformation between the weights of the neuron and incoming vector, adding a bias to the resulting scalar. Once the transform has been computed; the output corresponding to a non-linear function for the scalar output is calculated and propagated forward as the result of the particular neuron. The non-linear function in this scenario is called an *activation function*; namely these are functions like Sigmoid, ReLU, tanh, etc. In the output layer results from the previous layer are accumulated and using either a *SoftMax* or *ArgMax* function to predict the appropriate category for an input.

1.2.1 Non-Convolutional Neural Network

Linear Classifiers. Images are essentially three-dimensional matrices that can be linearized to form long vectors. For example, if the image has a resolution

of 32×32 with RGB colour channels, it can be linearized to a vector with 3072 ($32 \times 32 \times 3$). this can be interpreted as a point in a 3072 dimensional space. For a classification problem with k categories we can have k individual classifiers with 3072 parameters each. This gives rise to hyperplanes that divide the 3072 dimensional space into spaces containing *True* and *False* values for each categories.

Figure 1.4: Image vectors can be thought of as n-dimensional points

This can be thought of as a Neural Network with one hidden layer with k nodes. The total number of parameters for this model would be $3072 \times k$ (3072 parameters for each of the k classes). However, this is not nearly expressive enough to ensure proper classification, mostly because the limited number of parameters that the model has access to and the rigid nature of the decision boundaries (collection of hyperplanes in this case). Adding more hidden layers and activation functions significantly increases the expressiveness of these neural network models by adding complexity and flexibility in how the decision boundary for each class is defined.

1.3 Convolutional Neural Networks.

The models converting images into an input vector do not show any significant improvements in accuracy despite being more computationally complex than traditional methods. By linearizing the image into an input vector disregards all three invariant properties of images that need to be preserved. Decomposing the image into a column vector removes all spatial information in the image

along with removing the ability to detecting edges thereby preventing it from detecting the rich featural hierarchy that can be detected from the image.

Convolutional Neural Networks [18] account for these factors and modern architectures have systems built into them to ensure higher accuracy during prediction. The three main factors that the CNNs introduce that is specifically adapted for analysing images are: **Convolution**, **ReLU (Activation Functions)**, **(Max) Pooling**.

CNNs contains *Convolution Blocks* consisting of the Convolution operation, Activation Functions and Pooling layers. These operations are repeated over and over again in order to increase depth of the network and the number of parameters available to the model.

Figure 1.5: Convolution Block for a CNN

These repeated Convolution Blocks compress information present in the picture while preserving the important spatial and gradient-level details in the image. These operations performs feature extraction and reduces the entire image into a vector array. The resulting array is then fed into a Fully Connected layer for propagation through multiple hidden layers to the output layer for prediction. Previous algorithmic approaches to object recognition also used image processing as a way to extract significant features from the image. Previous feature extraction approach were rigid and did not adapt according to the data, current models *learn* feature extraction depending on the training data made available to these models. This is a way of reliably automating the process of information extraction from the image data and ensuring that the model adapts to data shifts and accounts for corner cases.

There are other methods that have been used over time in order to improve

accuracy of the base model such as Residual connections, Batch Normalization, Data Augmentation, Dropout and varying sizes of the convolutional filters. but the underlying backbone of image-centric Neural Networks remain the same. The details regarding the three main operations helps to demonstrate what their utility is and how they fit into the bigger picture of image recognition-related tasks.

1.3.1 Convolution

Figure 1.6: Convolution operation

The Convolution operation involves slides a smaller matrix on top of a larger matrix based on some stride s . The smaller matrix is often called either a kernel or a filter and the larger matrix is called a feature maps. At the input layer, the original image acts as the feature map that the kernel is convolved on. For any input I and known kernel K the result of convolution at position (i, j) can be given by:

$$O(i, j) = \sum_m \sum_n I(i + m, j + n) \cdot K(m, n)$$

where $O(i, j)$ is the output pixel value, and m, n range over the dimensions of the filter. The two main determining factors for the convolution operation are the dimensions of the kernels and the stride corresponding to each convolution operation. Convolutions in CNNs are performed by kernels over an input (image or feature maps) to get locality preserving feature maps. The kind of information that is preserved in the resulting feature map is dependent on the kernels and the stride for each kernel. One of the most famous kernels that are traditionally used are *Sobel filters* that are useful for detecting edge gradients in certain directions. For CNNs filters similar these are learning through the training process with

filters deeper and deeper into the network detecting more complex features from the input image.

Figure 1.7: The dimensions of the output feature map depends on the stride and filter dimensions

Each cell that the convolutional filter is comprised of is itself a neuron that learns a weight during training time. There are multiple such filters bundled together to form a particular convolutional layer. So for a layer where there are p convolutional filters each having a dimension of $m \times n$, the total number of neurons for that particular layers is $p \times m \times n$. Although this may seem counter-intuitive, organizing the neurons in such a way increases efficiency by introducing parameters sharing in CNNs. If we consider a fully connected neural network wherein each pixel is uniquely connected to all of the neurons in the preceding layer there is an explosion in the number of parameters that are required to ingest just a part of the image into the network. A greyscale picture with even 32 pixels values in height and width has a total of 1024 pixels, so for even just 5 neurons in the corresponding input layer, we will have 5120 parameters in just the first layer itself. For more realistic scenarios we can have hundred of thousands or even millions of parameters just in the first layer itself. Parameter sharing reduces the total number of parameters required to a manageable amount for more efficient learning. A filter or kernel is just a simple group of weights shared all over the input space. Since the convolution operation is performed by sliding the filter/kernel over a feature map, the weights are shared. Each weight is associated with a neuron and is able to see some *features* of the training image.

Figure 1.8: Highlighted features corresponding to filters for the digit 9 from the MNIST dataset [19]

1.3.2 Activation Functions

Activation functions are non-linearities introduced in neural networks that contribute a lot of expressiveness to these deep learning models. The activation function most generally used in CNNs is the *Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU)*. The ReLU function has the following form:

$$ReLU(x) = \begin{cases} x, & \text{if } x \geq 0 \\ 0, & \text{else} \end{cases}$$

Without activation functions like ReLU, all parameters would essentially be affine transformations which is not expressive enough to model real world data. Non-linear data needs to be accounted for to create a well-fitting approximation or classification model. Without activation function, all neural networks would collapse to form a simple linear classifier which has been demonstrated to be not complex enough to model visual data to a reasonable degree of accuracy.

Figure 1.9: ReLU is the most common activation function (non-linearity) actively used in CNNs

The ReLU function used in CNNs helps in preserving strong, highly correlated (positive) signals from the preceding feature maps. This function also removes negative activations so that incorrect associations are not learnt by the network or used to make predictions. Therefore ReLU sections in CNNs help the network to note which important patterns necessary for appropriate prediction. There are other activations that can be used such as Sigmoid, tanh or other variations of the ReLU function that can be adapted to be used in CNNs, however they have not been demonstrated to be as effective as ReLU for image-centric applications.

1.3.3 Pooling

Receptive Field of a Neuron

Figure 1.10: Convolutions determine the locality of the image that forms the receptive field of a neuron and pooling operation help in increasing the range that this receptive field covers

The Pooling operation is unique to CNNs and is used in order to down-sample feature maps. This is done to increase the receptive field of single neurons deeper into a neural network. The pooling operation is generally similar to a convolution operation. The difference in this case being that the kernel that is slid over the feature map does not perform the element-wise multiplication and cumulative summation operation. Instead, the kernel helps to select a section of the feature map to perform the Pooling operation. The pooling operation down-samples the elements of the selected patch by using a predefined operator and therefore condenses the signal of the patch to a single neuron.

Figure 1.11: Pooling operation acts as a method to down-sample the feature map of a layer

A receptive field is defined in the feature map, i.e., the output of convolution or ReLU operations and is represented as the set χ . All pixel cell values inside the neighbourhood is defined as $z_{i,j}^{(n)} \in \chi$, where $z_{i,j}^{(n)}$ refers to the cell with coordinates (i, j) in the n -th layer of the CNN.

There are multiple ways to compute the pooling operation in a CNNs, two of them have been highlighted below:

Mean Pooling. Mean or Average Pooling is a pooling operation in which the mean or average operator is used to down-samples the elements of a selected patch of the preceding feature map. For elements inside the patch, their mean is calculated and the mean value is then the output value for the corresponding neuron. Elements inside the patch are considered to be inside the neighbourhood χ where $z_{i,j}^{(n)} \in \chi$ correspond to the receptive field of $z_{p,q}^{(n+1)}$, a neuron of the next immediately next layer.

$$x_{p,q}^{(n+1)} = AvgPool(\chi) = \frac{\sum_i^{|\chi|} z_i^{(n)}}{|\chi|}$$

Min Pooling. Min Pooling selects the darker pixels from the feature map. As an image processing technique it is useful when the background of the image is bright and we are selectively interested in the darker pixels of the image. This is generally not utilized in CNN algorithms.

$$x_{p,q}^{(n+1)} = MinPool(\chi) = \min_{x_{i,j}^{(n)} \in \chi} z_{i,j}^{(n)}$$

Max Pooling. Max Pooling [16] is the most frequently used pooling operation. In Max Pooling, we have a $MaxPool(\chi)$ function that takes a set of elements, each of which belong to a set χ . Where χ is the neighbourhood in the preceding layer that contains all the cells that fall inside the receptive field of $x_{p,q}^{(n+1)}$ neuron. This function preserves the strongest signal received from the previous layers. Where the strength of a signal is determined by the magnitude of how positive the corresponding cell in the feature map is. The pooling operation also helps in increase the patch of the image that is visible to the neurons in the deeper layer of the network. This helps in processing spatial information and hierarchy of features similar to what has been seen for image processing in the biological context. [13] [12] [33]

$$x_{p,q}^{(n+1)} = MaxPool(\chi) = \max_{x_{i,j} \in \chi} z_{i,j}$$

An important thing to keep note of is that so far all of the non-linear activation functions introduced are monotonically increasing, including ReLU. Due to some special properties of the ReLU function, namely that it filters out negative inputs and returns exact values for positive values, the order of MaxPool and ReLU in the layers does not matter. This can be demonstrated mathematically as:

$$\max(f(x_1), f(x_2), \dots, f(x_n)) = f(\max(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n))$$

Thus, in the computation blocks the arrangement of ReLU and MaxPool functions is interchangeable.

1.4 Object Detection

The standard CNN architecture is suitable for image recognition or classification tasks which is generally a single stage task. In order to additionally include object localization for given images, we need supporting mechanisms that predict *bounding boxes* to confine said objects. Object Classification is a label prediction task with c -categories and although Object Detection is a Supervised Learning task in a similar vein, their loss functions are of differing methodologies which need to be setup accordingly.

Figure 1.12: Classification is a single-step c -class prediction task

For Object Detection a **Bounding Box Regressor** is needed to predict the x, y coordinates along with the width and height of the bounding box. This requires a regression loss function (such as MSE) as compared to a classification loss function such as Cross-Entropy Loss. BBox (Bounding Box) Regression does not necessarily depend on the classification prediction task and thus can be implemented parallelly in order to avoid setting up their loss functions together. A CNN backbone is required in order to perform feature extraction, this gives us dimensionally reduced feature maps that can be flattened and fed into a *Classification Head* and *Regression Head* separately to get their corresponding predictions.

Figure 1.13: Object Detection Task (for single object) consists of a CNN backbone and two prediction heads

Therefore, so far the Object Detection methodology consists of a singular Convolutional backbone that performs feature extraction. Then the output feature map is flattened and used as the input vector to both the Classification and Regression Head predicting the class of the object and location of the object respectively. This is also the general approach that has been iteratively improved upon in order to get better localization, boosting the general accuracy and reducing total runtime overhead. A bird's eye view of the same model for

object detection can be seen below:

Figure 1.14: Object Detection task in a nutshell

However, there are several problems one runs into when implementing such a simplistic framework to solve object detection. The most significant contributor to the problems faced during object detection is localization. Objects do not all come in uniform shapes and sizes. Different sizes and different aspect ratios need to be considered for the bbox regressor in order to accurately predict required bounding boxes. We can use a sliding window approach by taking patches of the input image as inputs to the regressor network. However in that case we will need to consider multiple aspect ratios and strides for the sliding window. There is also the uncertain factor of how many objects we want to detect. This means that there are too many unknowns that need to be accounted for under a simple sliding window approach. Thus, at a glance the following problems need to be addressed in order for an object detection network to function successfully:

- **Variable sized outputs:** there may be 1 occurrence of a class C or 100, output needs to be adaptable w.r.t that.
- **Inter-Class and Intra-Class Distinction:** Where does one object end and another start, i.e., distinct separation between objects.
- **Region Localization:** Where to look in order to identify objects, brute force search will not always work due to an explosion in search space. This will also determine the size and shape of bounding boxes that should be used for confining objects.

In the above list of hurdles facing Object Detection tasks, the third barrier is a significant problem without solving which any possible work on the rest of the barriers is completely intractable. Accounting for variable output sizes and proper Class distinction is futile unless we can identify neighbourhoods of interest to perform more targeted object detection tasks instead of blind brute force search. Therefore a possible solution might be to utilize some transformations

on training/test images to identify areas of interest and search on the restricted search space. In this regard previously mentioned algorithmic approaches can be utilized such as some variations of Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG) [4], Deformable Parts Model (DPM) [5], etc.

1.4.1 Region Proposals

One of the most successful and widely used algorithmic techniques that can be used for generating region of interests is called *Selective Search* [1]. It can be used to restrict the search space of the input image by segmenting the image into a collection of patches on which a brute force search can be done at a significantly less time and computational overhead.

Selective Search. Selective Search is an algorithm used primarily to generate region proposals for objects within an image.

Figure 1.15: Each pixel is converted to a node v_i with edges e_{ij} connecting it to its surrounding pixels with a certain weight $w(e_{ij})$

It is a graph-based algorithm that transforms the input image into a graph $G = (V, E)$ where each pixel is a node in the graph and the vertices connect neighbouring pixels together. Weights are assigned to the edges of the graph based on the colour differences between two pixels:

$$w(e_{ij}) = \sqrt{(R_i - R_j)^2 + (G_i - G_j)^2 + (B_i - B_j)^2}$$

where R , G and B are the colour channels of the image. The image is initially segmented into small regions using a method like Felzenszwalb and Huttenlocher's graph-based segmentation algorithm [6]. This results in superpixels, which are relatively uniform in terms of color and texture. The smaller regions generated are then recursively combined into larger regions. The regions

are combined based on similarity scores generated using different metrics like Colour, Texture, Size and Shape. The methods used to calculate similarities with respect to previously mentioned criteria between two neighbouring regions are as follows:

$$S_{\text{color}}(R_i, R_j) = \sum_k \min(H_{R_i}(k), H_{R_j}(k))$$

$$S_{\text{texture}}(R_i, R_j) = \sum_k \min(T_{R_i}(k), T_{R_j}(k))$$

$$S_{\text{size}}(R_i, R_j) = 1 - \frac{|R_i| + |R_j|}{|I|}$$

$$S_{\text{shape}}(R_i, R_j) = 1 - \frac{B_{ij}}{|B_i \cup B_j|}$$

The similarity scores generated based on these techniques is then used in a predefined weighted sum

$$S(R_i, R_j) = \alpha S_{\text{color}}(R_i, R_j) + \beta S_{\text{texture}}(R_i, R_j) + \gamma S_{\text{size}}(R_i, R_j) + \delta S_{\text{shape}}(R_i, R_j)$$

in order to combine the regions into a hierarchy based on similarities. These practices helps in creating *region proposals* or patches of the image where an object might be located. The granularity of the region proposals can be determined using the hierarchies of merged regions. One of the significant CNN architectures that utilizes this method is *Regions with CNN features* or *R-CNNs*. R-CNNs able to then generate region proposals based on which object detection and classification takes place.

Figure 1.16: Hierarchy of segmented patches can help in determining object locality [37]

1.5 R-CNN family

1.5.1 R-CNN

Figure 1.17: Basic architecture of a R-CNN

The R-CNN architecture is one of the first modified CNN models that was aimed specifically at addressing the problem of object detection. Based on utilizing algorithmic means to find *Regions of Interest (RoIs)* in the image and treating each region proposal as input images.

The input image is taken and Selective Search is applied on it to generate approximately 2000 region proposals. These region proposals are then warped and dilated to form a set of individual input images that are each of the same dimensions. These input images are propagated through the CNN backbone (AlexNet [16] in case of the original implementation). The feature vector extracted from the image is in turn propagated through two fully connected layers (Regression and Classification head) to predict the class of the object and corresponding coordinates for the same. For classification, we have $c + 1$ categories instead of the standard c categories. The new classes are: c original classes and 1 background class.

Bounding Box Regression. The Regressor does not directly predict the coordinates of the bounding box in the input image itself. For every box proposal $B_p = (x_p, y_p, w_p, h_p)$ (made as per the region proposals), we have a ground truth bounding box $B_g = (x_g, y_g, w_g, h_g)$. The goal of the bounding box regressor is to predict the offset (or transformation) from the proposal box to the ground truth box which will be of the form:

$$t_x = \frac{x_g - x_p}{w_p}, \quad t_y = \frac{y_g - y_p}{h_p}$$
$$t_w = \log\left(\frac{w_g}{w_p}\right), \quad t_h = \log\left(\frac{h_g}{h_p}\right)$$

The predicted offsets will be the output in vector form, each of whose elements will be: $\hat{t}_x, \hat{t}_y, \hat{t}_w, \hat{t}_h$. Applying the predicted offsets to the proposed bounding

box we obtain the refined bounding box:

$$\begin{aligned}x_r &= \hat{t}_x \cdot w_p + x_p, & y_r &= \hat{t}_y \cdot h_p + y_p \\w_r &= w_p \cdot \exp(\hat{t}_w), & h_r &= h_p \cdot \exp(\hat{t}_h)\end{aligned}$$

Non-Maximum Suppression. Consider that there are two bounding box proposals covering the same underlying object. In this case, which particular bounding box will be selected as the resultant bounding box. This is determined using *Non-Maximum Suppression (NMS)*. NMS is an algorithm that takes as data the list of bounding box proposals covering the same object and returns the most fitting proposal. How well a particular bbox proposal covers a certain object is calculated via their Intersection over Union (IoU) values. The IoU value is calculated by taking the ground truth bbox and proposed bbox and calculating how well the proposal overlaps the ground truth:

$$IoU = \frac{|A \cap B|}{|A \cup B|}$$

The common area shared by the proposed bbox and ground truth divided by the area that these two bounding boxes share in common presents the metric to determine accurately how much the proposal overlaps with the ground truth. Thus NMS consists of calculating the IoUs for all proposals when the object is same for all the bounding boxes and only picking the proposal with the highest overlap by suppressing all of the remaining proposals. IoU can be interpreted as a way of calculating precision of a proposal, in terms of a confusion matrix, an IoU can be calculated in the following way:

$$IoU = \frac{TP}{TP + FP + FN}$$

where, TP is True Positive, FP is False Positive and FN is False Negative.

mAP. *Mean Average Precision (mAP)* is a standard metric for evaluating object detection models over multiple iterations. Precision and Recall is used heavily to calculate said metric. *Precision* corresponds to the proportion of correct identifications amongst all predictions, or how many bboxes out of the total are predicting an object. *Recall* corresponds to the model's ability to detect all correct samples or how many of the ground truth values were detected correctly.

We use the area under the Precision vs Recall graph to calculate the *Average Precision* of the model for a particular instance of a class in a given input image. This process is then repeated for all possible object classes and given input image dataset in order to calculate the mean Average Precision (mAP) for the model. The overall sensitivity of the model under different IoU thresholds can also be similarly calculated by modulating the threshold value at which the NMS algorithm operates. We can generate the total mAP of the model over a range

of threshold values, thereby determining how the model works under different circumstances.

Figure 1.18: R-CNN Architecture

Drawbacks

The two major drawbacks of the R-CNN algorithm is the expensive and multi-stage training process that is both compute and time intensive and the amount of memory it consumes at runtime. During training all object proposals need to be stored in memory for training. Thus, all 2000 object proposal features are independently stored. Beyond that the algorithmic process of generation Regions of Interests (RoIs) is time-intensive, The algorithm is so very slow at test time, that it becomes unsuitable for real-time tasks. This architecture cannot be feasibly applied to systems that require a short feedback cycle operating in real-time scenarios. Additionally all detected object proposals need to be propagated through the CNN layers to generate their corresponding feature vector. This implies that the computations in the convolutional blocks of the CNN layers have to be repeated multiple times (2000 times). This is a clear bottleneck in the algorithm that needs to be addressed in order to achieve a more efficient runtime. Region proposals are essentially patches of the image that are of interest due to some intrinsic pattern, texture or structure of the image. This process can equivalently be carried out on a feature map. Upon

this conclusion the *fast R-CNN* architecture has been constructed.

Figure 1.19: The time and compute-intensive nature of the R-CNN algorithm makes it a less attractive choice for efficient object detection tasks

1.5.2 Fast R-CNN

The Fast R-CNN architecture [9] has been designed to mitigate the flaws of the R-CNN by restricting the number of times convolutional operations have to be computed following the selective search algorithm. Object proposals are located on the feature map by utilizing scaling transformations to the corresponding regions generated from the input directly rather propagating them through the CNN backbone thousands of times. The CNN backbones popularly utilized in case to extract the feature maps are pre-trained convolutional neural networks like VGG16 [29] or ResNet [11]. Instead of generating regions of interest in the input image itself and then repeatedly propagating the proposals through the CNN backbone, the fast R-CNN algorithm generates regions of interest and locates them on the top of the feature map generated by the CNN backbone. This leads to a phenomenal speed-up in the execution time taken by the algorithm. However this does nothing to address the memory consumption of the R-CNN architecture as the object proposals still require to be stored during training.

Fast R-CNN

Figure 1.20: Block Diagram of a fast R-CNN architecture

The object proposals on feature maps are generated by *Selective Search* (similar to R-CNNs). These object proposals are of irregular sizes and are therefore condensed to uniform dimensions using a technique called *RoI Pooling*. The pooled proposals are flattened into feature vectors and passed through both classification and bounding box regression fully connected layers. Fast R-CNN also integrates generating region proposals, extracting features and training the classifier into a single-stage process. The original R-CNN performs object detection through a multi-stage training process, i.e., its component performing activities like feature extraction, bbox regression and classification have to be trained individually before they are combined together into the R-CNN architecture. Multi-stage training becomes tedious for large enough networks and it drastically lowers the speed of the model.

Note: In almost all Object Detection algorithms pre-trained CNN backbones are used as feature extractors. This reduces the overhead of training CNN non-Fully Connected layers by reusing previously created models that have proven to work well.

RoI Pooling. RoI (Region of Interest) Pooling helps in efficiently extracting fixed-size feature maps from regions of interest in an image, regardless of their original size. This is done in order to propagate a fixed sized vector through the deeper layers of the network as most sections of a neural network expect a fixed input size. The input vector of any fully connected neural network will have a fixed number of elements that it can propagate through the network.

Figure 1.21: RoI Pooling [20] reduces object proposals by max pooling within each grid cell

After a feature map has been extracted from an image, Regions of interest are proposed areas in the image that are likely to contain objects. Each RoI is represented as a rectangular bounding box on the feature map, with coordinates defining its position and size. The RoI's coordinates (from the original input image) are mapped to the corresponding coordinates on the feature map by scaling the RoI coordinates proportionally, based on the downsampling factor of the CNN. Once the RoI is located on the feature map, it is divided into a grid of fixed-size sub-regions depending on the dimensions of desired object proposal outputs. Within each grid cell max pooling is performed and maximum value from the sub-region of the feature map occupy the corresponding position in the resulting grid cell. Thus for each grid cell only the strongest signal is preserved and the object proposals are all condensed to a uniform dimension that can be fed into proceeding layers.

The rest of the operations mentioned above like: *Non-Maximum Suppression*, *mean Average Precision* work in this algorithm similarly as to R-CNNs. Non-Maximum Suppression (NMS) is used to suppress all other bounding boxes that have lesser overlap with the ground truth than the bounding box with the highest overlap. Mean Average Precision (mAP) is the metric used to calculate the degree of accuracy for the model over a range of different threshold values across different categories. A point to remember is that in all of

Drawbacks

The fast R-CNN model successfully removes the bottleneck that arises from propagating thousands of object proposal through the CNN backbone. However, a new bottleneck is observed in this new model.

Figure 1.22: The algorithmic region proposal generation becomes the bottleneck for fast R-CNN models

Selective Search, in the context of fast R-CNNs, becomes a bottleneck in the detection pipeline. This reliance on computationally expensive and slow region proposal methods like Selective Search to generate regions of interest (RoIs) incurs additional latency in the system. Although fast R-CNN is faster than R-CNN, it still struggles with real-time performance, particularly when processing high-resolution images or large datasets.

1.5.3 Faster R-CNN

Figure 1.23: Block Diagram for a Faster R-CNN architecture

Fast R-CNN is outperformed by Faster R-CNN [28], which are end-to-end trained networks containing their own region proposals generation technique

directly working inside the network itself. Faster R-CNN integrates all stages of the object detection pipeline into one single, unified network.

Region Proposal Network

Faster R-CNNs do not use an external algorithm to predict object proposals. *Region Proposal Networks (RPNs)* are the core innovation of Faster R-CNN. They generate region proposals directly from the feature map produced by the convolutional layers of the CNN, without relying on an external algorithm like Selective Search. A pre-trained CNN backbone such as VGG16 [29] takes the image as an input and generates a feature map that will be used by the RPN to create a set of region proposals. The RPN slides a small network (often a 3x3 convolutional layer) over the feature map and generates a set of candidate bounding boxes (referred to as *anchors*) with different sizes and aspect ratios at each location. For each anchor, the RPN predicts whether it contains an object (which is called its *objectness score*) and refines its bounding box coordinates.

Figure 1.24: The output generated for an example RPN

The RPN uses a small sliding window (usually a 3x3 convolutional filter) that moves across the entire feature map produced by a CNN backbone. This sliding window looks at every location on the feature map and predicts whether that location could be the center of an object. At each location of the sliding window, a set of predefined bounding boxes, known as *anchors*, are generated. Anchors have different scales (sizes) and aspect ratios (1:1, 1:2 and 2:1) to cover a wide variety of object shapes and sizes. Typically, 9 anchors (3 scales \times 3 aspect ratios) are generated per sliding window location.

RPNs work on the assumption that universally there are three main standard geometries for bounding boxes that can be summarized by the three aspect

ratios being considered at multiple scales. Therefore, for the feature map corresponding to input images, we will have a small network of sliding over the map, the network is of 3×3 size and is used to increase the receptive field. Then the resulting feature map is convolved with two more 1×1 networks.

Figure 1.25: Anchor boxes generated at the center of a grid cell

The two 1×1 networks return vectors with the total number of elements being $4K$ and $2K$ respectively, where K is the number of categories that the entire network can recognize. The two branches of the RPN predict two things:

- $1 \times 1 \times 4K$: Transformations for Bounding Box coordinates along with width and height corresponding each of the K categories :

$$[\mathcal{P}(0,t_x), \mathcal{P}(0,t_y), \mathcal{P}(0,t_w), \mathcal{P}(0,t_h), \dots, \mathcal{P}(K,t_w), \mathcal{P}(K,t_h)]_{1 \times 4K}$$

- $1 \times 1 \times 2K$: Objectness Score corresponding to each of the K categories. Each object has two confidence scores assigned to it; one determining if the object is an actual example of the category and another determining whether it is not actually an example of the class :

$$[\mathcal{P}(0,obj), \mathcal{P}(0,bg), \dots, \mathcal{P}(K,obj), \mathcal{P}(K,bg)]_{1 \times 2K}$$

The RPN is the underlying technique that enables region proposal generation faster than algorithmic methods like Selective Search. This removes the previously held bottleneck and makes the model end-to-end trainable. Other than RPNs faster R-CNNs continue to use RoI pooling to ensure the region proposals are uniform in their dimensions. However despite improvements in the overall performance in faster R-CNN, they are still not capable enough to be deployed into real-time applications without major updates to the algorithm.

Figure 1.26: A flowchart of the standard RPN convolutions with their respective dimensions. The CNN backbone used in this generic example is ZFNet [40].

Drawbacks

Faster R-CNN are still not quick and reliable enough to be utilized in real-time applications. Although end-to-end training is done in Faster R-CNN, it is a two step process. But if we want a one stage network that can do object class detection and bounding box regression in a single shot, that is not possible by Faster R-CNNs.

1.6 YOLO

Figure 1.27: Block Diagram of a YOLO [26] network

Instead of two stage networks that predicts boxes and classes separately, YOLO introduces a single shot object detection and classification pipeline. This is done by framing it as a single regression problem rather than a series of classification problems. YOLO v1 has a procedure very similar to that of Faster R-CNN, partitioning input image/feature map in a collection of grid cells. Instead of a sliding window approach with predetermined anchor boxes, the input image is divide into a $S \times S$ grid. S is usually equal to values like 7 or 19, so there are in total 49 or 361 grid cells that the image is divided into. Each grid cell is responsible for detecting objects whose center falls within that cell. Each grid cell predicts a fixed number of bounding boxes (usually 2).

The model predicts the x, y coordinates of the center of the image relative to the grid cell and the width, height relative to the image. The two bounding boxes predicted will each have their own confidence scores that will signify the degree of certainty with which the model determines whether an object is confined by the bounding boxes or not. The confidence score is defined as:

$$Pr(Object) \times IoU_{\text{truth}}^{\text{pred}}$$

where $Pr(Object)$ is the probability that an object is present and IoU is the Intersection over Union between the predicted box and the ground truth box.

Each grid cell also predicts a probability distribution over the possible c object classes. This probability is independent of the bounding boxes and represents the likelihood of each class being present in the grid cell. The area that

each grid cell covers is fixed. YOLO uses a novel approach to object detection by framing it as a single regression problem rather than a series of classification problems as seen before.

Figure 1.28: Relative coordinates of the bounding box with respect to the image

Each grid cell covers a predefined fixed portion of the image, regardless of the object's actual size or shape. This rigid grid structure simplifies the detection process by localizing it to specific regions of the image but it also introduces some limitations, especially for smaller objects. If there are multiple objects inside one grid cell, YOLO will have problems. Each grid cell has the task of predicting a single object although multiple bounding boxes are generated. A particular point to keep in mind is that the grid-based structure is not explicitly maintained throughout the neural network's layers but rather is an implicit part of the final output layer's structure. This is in stark comparison to the R-CNN family that has some multi-stage process of explicitly picking out regions of interest and then passing them through a standard classifier.

To demonstrate that, we follow the inference process in a YOLO architecture. The input image is resized to conform to standard YOLO input dimensions (e.g., 448x448 pixels for YOLO v1 or 416x416 pixels for YOLO v3). The pixels will be normalized to a range of $[0, 1]$ and the corresponding feature map is generated by propagating the normalized image through the CNN backbone (e.g., GoogLeNet) and downsampling it. The feature map is conceptually divided into an $S \times S$ grid when flattened and passed through a set of fully connected layers.

This is ensured by having the resulting tensor having dimensions $S \times S \times q$ where q is the total number of elements predicted for each grid cell.

1.6.1 Output Tensor

The $S \times S \times q$ dimensional output vector is comprised of a collection of q dimensional vectors. Each of the S^2 vectors contain q elements predicted by the model are the coordinates of the two bounding boxes, their corresponding confidence score and a probability distribution over the set of object categories. A detailed representation of the same is given below:

Figure 1.29: The output tensor corresponding to the YOLOv1 algorithm is where the grid structure is constructed

YOLO v1 directly predicts bounding boxes and class probabilities from the entire image in a single forward pass through the network making it extremely fast and suitable for real-time applications. However it is far from ideal in a lot of circumstances. It can operate with a capacity of 45 frames per second, however, the mAP for the same is 63.4% [26].

There are multiple architectures that have been introduced to address the shortcomings of the YOLO architecture. But YOLO v1 and its subsequent versions have been the gold standard for multi-object detection in a real-time setting.

1.7 Object Detection in Videos

Object detection in video media is a more complex task as compared to static images due to an additional temporal considerations that is added to the de-

tection and localization process. Consistently following a distinct object over a period of time is a separate and sufficiently hard problem known as *object tracking*.

This involves not just detecting objects in each individual frame, but also ensuring temporal consistency with object tracking across multiple frames. The basic technique in video object detection involves applying object detection techniques to each frame, but advanced methods also incorporate tracking and temporal smoothing to improve accuracy and reduce noise.

1.7.1 Rolling Averages approach

Figure 1.30: Simple Rolling Averages Video Classification

The simplest approach is to treat each frame of the video as a separate input image and apply a standard object detection algorithm (like YOLO or Faster R-CNN as seen above) to detect objects in each frame independently. Although this is a straightforward method with a relatively high baseline due to the strength of the underlying object detection algorithm. However, this approach may lead to inconsistent detections across frames due to factors like motion blur, changes in lighting, rapid object movement and occlusion. Thus a better approach would be to take overlapping samples from the video feed and make a prediction based on their overall average predictions. The output is the expected predictions resulting from a set of cumulative outputs. This avoids prediction *flickering* that can occur due to misclassifications.

For any sequence of video frames at t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n we take subsets of the sequence that are temporally overlapping segments in the video. For each point in time we take the corresponding video frame and propagate through the network in order to get a prediction. The predictions for each of the subsets are calculated and assigned to roughly the appropriate time-step. Continuing this

process, for a fast enough CNN model, we can generate a real-time object detection system.

This model of object tracking on video might not be robust to perturbations or disturbances in the video feed. Robustness can be ensured using other algorithmic techniques to force temporal consistency of the predictions.

1.7.2 Late Fusion Architecture

Figure 1.31: Late Fusion Architecture

Late Fusion architecture takes place after convolution. The primary processes of this particular approach are identical to the Rolling Averages approach, however, instead of propagating the image sampled from the video feed through to the entire CNN to produce predictions at each temporal point, the images are propagated through a CNN backbone to extract the feature map of said image.

The extracted feature maps are then flattened and concatenated together in order to concatenate them together. This concatenated vector represents the overall feature of the particular video subsection that is currently being examined. This concatenated vector is then passed through *Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP)* in order to generate the required predictions. This is called a *late fusion* approach as the temporal information is being fused together at a very late phase in the architecture.

This process of late fusing temporal features can lead to the creation of sub-optimal features. The relative length of the concatenated vectors generated at the end of feature extraction can cause non-efficient object detection. Also,

redundant features might be recorded which added with a lot of extra tunable parameters may lead to overfitting. This was one of the first ways that image classification was applied to video clips by accounting for the temporal axis in conjunction with the standard image classification or object detection setup of CNN architectures.

1.7.3 Pool Late Fusion

Figure 1.32: Late Fusion Architecture with Pooling of features

Average pooling is a viable way to account for time in a video clip. The barrier that is faced when training such a model is the large number of parameters and the redundancy of space and time features that lead to overfitting. Thus, to mitigate this problem a global pooling layer can be introduced. This layer does pooling over space and time. The pooling operation replaces the flattening layer and helps in preserving the strongest features over space and time. The 2D CNN architectures produce independent features and corresponding features are passed through a pooling operation that will collapse all spatial information and temporal information into a d -dimensional vector, on which linear or MLP layers can be applied thus giving the required class scores.

Since this is also a late fusion modeling, it can give rise to sub-optimal fusion of information. This can be explicitly seen in the inability of the late fusion architectures to model for or analyze very low-level pixel information such as fine-grained motion between video frames. It is difficult for the model to learn

all the low-level interactions between the pixels in the adjacent frames of the input video clips. Late fusion architectures help in summarizing all the features of a particular set of inputs in a final feature vector thus the changes in pixel values at a certain position and how surrounding pixel values change in response to that remain unavailable to these models.

1.7.4 Early Fusion Architecture

Figure 1.33: Early Fusion providing details on a pixel-level hierarchy

To account for the shortcomings of the late fusion architectures, alternatives called *early fusion* architectures are used. One of the primary examples of the same is the utilization of the standard 2D Convolutions on a reshaped input data. In the 2D CNNs approach we take a standard CNN without making changes to it. Instead we reshape the input video to conform to the expected input dimensions of 2D convolutions. A video clip over time T can be represented as a 4-dimensional matrix of the dimensions $T \times 3 \times H \times W$ where H and W are the height and width of the input array respectively. Thus, the multidimensional array representing the input video file with 3 colour channels will undergo the following transformation:

$$T \times 3 \times H \times W \rightarrow 3T \times H \times W$$

The convolution and pooling operations will take place over this transformed array. The resulting array will have the temporal dimension represented as a set of channels with respect to the standard representation of inputs in CNNs. This method provides access to pixel level information to the network, but it is collapsed into a standard tensor faster than the network can learn from them.

This approach collapses all temporal information into a resulting feature map. It does not preserve the temporal information relevant for appropriate predictions. Aggressive collapse of the temporal information might not be a sufficient criteria to learn pixel-level interaction at any reasonably good level.

1.7.5 3D Convolutional Networks

Figure 1.34: 3D CNN Architecture

A 3D CNN or a slow fusion network maintains a 4-dimensional feature map at each layer of its architecture. Three dimensional analogs of the convolution operation will be utilized along with two dimensional analogs of pooling. These types of networks propagate four dimensional tensors (with two spatial dimensions, one temporal and one channel dimension) through the network slowly fusing the temporal information to inform the predictions. Input for 3D CNNs:

$$T \times 3 \times H \times W$$

This approach is called the slow fusion approach as it builds a receptive field over both time and space slowly throughout the network. in comparison the previous late fusion architectures were building receptive fields in space slowly over all each individual frames and then the receptive field over time was built all-at-once when a pooling or concatenation operation took place at the *end* to combine the independent individual learned features in a vector representing the entire video sample. Similarly, the 2D CNN approach network has access to the all of the temporal feature at the first step and thus the receptive field over time was built all-at-once at the *start* of the process.

One of the main differences between the 2D CNN and the 3D CNN approach is unavailability of temporal invariance in the 2D CNN approach. This happens

due to the filters of 2D CNN approach extend the full breadth of time that is stacked together into one tensor. To pinpoint transitions in pixel values from one colour to another 2D Convolutions will require two filters with different parameters. Other than that the convolutions will be sensitive to the order of stacking for the tensor. Since filters in 3D CNNs would occupy a much smaller area in both time and space, 3D convolutions will be more accurately be able to pinpoint shifts with only one filter meanwhile also not being sensitive to the ordering of frames. 3d CNNs are temporal shift invariant thus enabling to identify the same thing happening in different points of time. This implies that 3D CNNs are more representationally efficient for videos.

1.8 Conclusion

Over this report neural networks and their variants in the visual context have been defined. This includes a discuss on the model architectures that are simple classifiers without any convolutional functions. This was followed details on Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and the fundamental operation that they are comprised of (ReLU, Convolution and Pooling). The fundamental operations of CNNs were briefly described with their contributions to the prediction process being briefly determined.

Once a relevant exposition on CNNs were completed, a description of the problem of (multi-object) detection was given along with the naive, brute-force solution (sliding window). Since the naive solution was not feasible under current computational constraints more constrained solutions, including region proposals were discussed. One possible mechanism for generating region proposals were described and their utility in constricting the search space for an object detection problem led into the first family of CNN architectures expressly designed to be utilized for such. The R-CNN family of architectures were described along with the various quirks, advantages and disadvantages of each. Each member of the family demonstrated incremental improvements in multi-stage object detection capabilities. The notable point was a shift away from more algorithmic approaches to more neural network approaches. One way these models reduced the required execution time is avoiding multiple forward propagations in a deep network. This was a noticeable bottleneck that vastly improved the performance of Fast R-CNN over the R-CNN architecture. Next came the introduction of Region Proposal Networks (RPNs) in Faster R-CNNs. So far none of the models designed for object detection were capable of being adapted to real-time systems due to the time taken for execution. An entirely new single stage architecture called YOLO (You Only Look Once) was introduced to fit this need. YOLO models have the capacity to operate much higher fps rates at the cost of lesser accuracy. Incremental improvements to the YOLO architecture such as the YOLO v3 [27] (utilizing the DarkNet [25] CNN backbone) have accomplished noticeable improvements on the pioneering models. These models can be used for real-time systems with the necessary guarantees in place to ensure the robustness of these models. Lastly the various techniques

to perform object detection were explained. Considered techniques consisted of late fusion models, early fusion 2D CNN models and 3D CNN models. Other more advanced techniques such as SORT or DeepSORT, particle filtering, etc. were not discussed as they fall under the purview of object tracking, i.e, the process of following the movement of one or more detected objects with, unique identities, across multiple frames in a video. There are additional localization techniques on top of the object detection techniques that have been discussed. For the purposes of automation along a fixed path (like rail lines) in most cases object detection is sufficient. For verticals with additional axes of freedom object tracking is more pertinent in order to successfully deploy collision avoidance systems, etc.

Chapter 2

Testing & Verification of Neural Networks

2.1 Introduction

For any reasonably complex system, it is necessary to ensure that the system is acting as intended without any unpredictable behaviours that may end up compromising the system and/or the systems surrounding it. There are many safety critical systems whose malfunctioning can cause innumerable casualties and loss of life, thus for these systems we need to reliably prove that they have predictable outputs corresponding to determined inputs.

Formal Verification utilizes a lot of different mathematical tools to demonstrate the *correctness* of some system with respect to some desirable specification or property. The set of tools used to formally verify some specification is collectively known as Formal Methods and include such theories as logic, automata, type systems and formal languages. These can be used to check the behaviour of some system against a set of specifications in order to determine correctness of the system. Formal Verification can be imagined as a layer of abstraction on top of systems (both software and hardware) that provides some mathematical guarantees as to the functioning of these systems.

Additionally Testing is also done in order to observe the behaviour of systems over known inputs. Testing does not guarantee the absence of errors or prove the correctness of a system. However, it is an efficient alternative to find bugs within the system and generally ensure proper functioning.

Below we will be building up to the application of Formal Methods to the field of Machine Learning in order to verify Neural Networks¹ and go over general Testing methodologies in the context of vision-focused Neural Network architectures.

¹The following is an effort to condense the Introduction to Neural Network Verification [2] book in order to concisely summarize the material that is relevant to my research.

2.2 Background

One of the first demonstrations of the possibilities of verification came from Alan Turing's 1949 paper called 'Checking a large routine' [35]. In the paper the program for finding the factorial of a number was broken down into a simple sequential set of instructions that could either be either *True* or *False*. The truth values for each of these assertions were then checked in order to prove that the program is a faithful implementation of the factorial mathematical function. This is known as proving the functional correctness of a program. Although this is the gold standard for demonstrating correctness, it is not possible to do so for Neural Networks² as the tasks performed cannot be precisely described mathematically. In a Neural Network we generally test for the following qualities:

- **Robustness** - This class of properties is violated when small perturbations to the inputs result in changes to the output. It also measures how well a model performs on new and unseen test data.
- **Safety** - This is a broad class of correctness properties that ensure that the program does not reach a 'bad' state. (e.g., a surgical robot should not be operating at 200mph).
- **Consistency** - This class of properties are violated only when the algorithms are not consistent with the real world. (e.g., tracking an object in free fall should be consistent with the laws of gravitation)

We will mostly be testing for Robustness, as that is the set of properties that are most widely tested for. It can also encapsulate the Safety and Consistency classes (as there is not well-defined boundary between them) if the specifications are designed accordingly.

2.2.1 Abstraction of Neural Network

We will not be dealing with the technicalities of the Neural Networks but rather use well-rounded mathematical abstractions that can be rigorously tested over. Since all Neural Networks can be thought of as *Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAGs)*, we will be treating them as such. More specifically they will be treated as dataflow graphs of operators over \mathbb{R} . The shape of these graphs will determine what specific architecture they belong to. Each node will perform some computation, whose dependencies are the edges. Thus, a neural network will be associated with some function:

$$f : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$$

For a Neural Network: $G = (V, E)$, we have:
 V : finite set of nodes

²Alan Turing had also extensively thought about 'learning networks' [36] that can be made from Boolean NAND networks learning over time.

$E \subseteq V \times V$: set of edges

$V^{in} \subset V$: input nodes

$V^o \subset V$: output nodes

n_v : total number of edges whose target is v

where, $n = |V^{in}|$ and $m = |V^o|$ for the network.

All neural networks are finite DAGs, there are classes of neural networks called Recurrent Neural Networks that have loops, but the number of iterations will depend on the size of the input. RNNs have self-loops that unroll based on the length of the input, which means that it reliably terminates. So while testing neural networks we will not test for loop termination and the explosion of possible program paths that comes with it.

Figure 2.1: RNNs are the only Neural Networks that have self-loops

For our purposes the following conditions must be met in a network:

- all nodes must be reachable from some input node
- every node can reach an output node
- fixed total ordering on edges E and another one on nodes V .

Each node v of the neural network is a function of the following form:

$$f_v : \mathbb{R}^{n_v} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

Where each node takes in some vector, does some computation on it and return a single output number that is passed through an activation function (a non-linear function), for ease of analysis they are treated as belonging to two different nodes. Each of the elements of the vectors are the outputs of previous nodes. These relations can be recursively defined with the base case terminating at the input nodes. Therefore, for every non-input node $v \in V$, we have:

Figure 2.2: Representation of a single node with incoming edges

Where each (v_i, v) represents an edge connecting node v_i to v . The ordering of these edges and nodes determines the inputs on the basis of which the computations will be done. Each node will have an $out(v)$ function which can be defined as follows:

$$out(v) = f_v(x_1, \dots, x_{n_v})$$

where $x_i = out(v_i)$ for $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n_v\}$. This is the recursive definition wherein each input to the node x_i can be defined as:

$$out(v) = f_v(out(v_1), out(v_2), \dots, out(v_{n_v}))$$

No sequence of operations are defined, only which nodes need what data to perform its computations. A more modified version of these graphs are known as **computation graphs**. $out(v_i)$ values can be computed in any topological ordering of graph nodes, as it needs to be ensured that all the inputs need to be computed before the target node itself. The total ordering ensures proper reference to the graph nodes and whether computations have been done in their desirable sequence, below the total ordering of nodes helps linearize the nodes into a topologically sorted sequence.

Figure 2.3: Representation of a Neural Network with two hidden layers and fixed total ordering of nodes.

All vector computations need to be linear:³

$$f(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n c_i x_i + b$$

or piece-wise linear:

$$f(x) \begin{cases} \sum_i c_i^{[1]} x_i + b^{[1]}, & x \in S_1 \\ \vdots \\ \sum_i c_i^{[m]} x_i + b^{[m]}, & x \in S_m \end{cases}$$

where $\cup_i S_i = \mathbb{R}^n$ and $\cap_i S_i = \emptyset$.

2.2.2 Defining Specifications

We define a language that specifies some properties about the functioning of a neural net. This will enable us to later on make statements and verify them based on the specifying language. *Specifications* are generally of the form:

$$\begin{aligned} &\{precondition\} \\ &\quad r \leftarrow f(x) \\ &\{postcondition\} \end{aligned}$$

³Neural Networks are an instance of differential programs.

where both preconditions and post-conditions are statements that specify some property that is adjacent to input and output respectively. Properties dictate the input-output behaviour of the network (and not the internals). Specifications help in quantifying some properties for accurate verification. Each specification can be thought of as being structured in the following way:

$\underbrace{\text{for inputs } x, y, \dots \text{ that } \dots}_{\text{precondition}} \text{ the neural network } G \text{ produces } \underbrace{\text{output that } \dots}_{\text{pstcondition}}$

Although every possible specification needed for complete verification cannot be made, multiple specifications can be combined together to test for stronger properties. Preconditions are generally predicates or Boolean functions defined over set of variables which act as inputs to the system, and post condition is a Boolean predicate over the variables appearing in precondition (x_i) and assigned variables (r_i). For any values of x_1, \dots, x_n that make the precondition true, let $r_1 = f(x_1), r_2 = g(x_2) \dots$, where $f(), g(), \dots$ are the computations on the input, then the post condition must also be *True*.

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\{\text{precondition}\} \\
 &\quad r_1 \leftarrow f(x_1) \\
 &\quad r_2 \leftarrow g(x_2) \\
 &\quad \vdots \\
 &\{\text{postcondition}\}
 \end{aligned}$$

If the post condition is *False*, then the correctness property is not true, i.e., the property does not hold.

Consider: c is an actual greyscale image, each element of c is the intensity of a pixel $\in (0, 1)$; we can state the following specification about the brightness of c and its corresponding classification:

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\{|x - c| \leq 0.1\} \\
 &\quad r_1 \leftarrow f(x) \\
 &\quad r_2 \leftarrow f(c) \\
 &\{\text{class}(r_1) = \text{class}(r_2)\}
 \end{aligned}$$

r_1 and r_2 are vectors whose elements are probabilities for a belonging to a class with labels corresponding to the indexes. $\text{class}(r_1)$ and $\text{class}(r_2)$ extract the indexes corresponding to the largest elements of the vectors r_1 and r_2 respectively.

Counterexamples: Valuations of variables in precondition that falsifies the post condition.

2.3 Constraint-Based Verification

A correctness property is taken and encoded as a set of constraints, solving which will help us to decide whether the property holds or not.

Let $fv(F)$ be the set of free variables appearing in the formula F .

Interpretation: I of F is a map from variables present in $fv(F)$ to either *True* or *False*. $I(F)$ denotes the formula where the variables have been replaced with their corresponding interpretations.

Example:

Let $F \triangleq (p \wedge q) \neg r$, which means that F is syntactically defined to be equal to the Boolean formula (as opposed to being semantically equivalent).

$$\begin{aligned}
 fv(F) &= \{p, q, r\} \\
 I &= \{p \mapsto \text{True}, q \mapsto \text{False}, r \mapsto \text{True}\} \\
 I(F) &\triangleq (\text{True} \wedge \text{False}) \neg \text{True}
 \end{aligned}$$

$eval(F)$: denotes the simplest form of F we can get by evaluating repeatedly. F is satisfiable (SAT) if there exists an I s.t.

- $eval(I(F)) = \text{True}$, in which case, I is the model of F : $I \models F$.
- $I \not\models F$ denotes I isn't a model of F .
- $I \not\models F$ if and only if $I \models \neg F$.
- F is unsatisfiable (UNSAT) if $\forall I, eval(I(F)) = \text{False}$.

Validity: If every interpretation I is a model of F , then F is valid.

Boolean satisfiability theories (SAT) can be generalised to more complex theories to include reals, vectors, strings, arrays, etc.; the problem of determining whether statements within these theories are true is known as *Satisfiability Modulo Theories* or simply SMT. We will be extensively using a first-order logic system called *Linear Real Arithmetic (LRA)* as it can represent a large class of neural networks and is decidable. In LRA, each propositional variable is replaced by a linear inequality of the form:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n c_i x_i + b \leq 0 \quad \text{OR} \quad \sum_{i=1}^n c_i x_i + b < 0$$

where $c_i, b \in \mathbb{R}$.

$$\left(\underbrace{x + y \leq 0}_p \wedge \underbrace{x - 2y < 10}_q \right) \vee \underbrace{x \geq 100}_r$$

An interpretation I of F is an assignment of every free variable to a real number.

2.3.1 Encoding Neural Networks

We need to translate Neural Networks into a formula in LRA such that we can use SMT Solvers (specialised software that tests satisfiability for SMT problems).

- f_v : Function in node.
- I : Model.
- F_v : Encoding for node.
- R_g : Relational mapping for neural network.

Whole Network can be defined as a binary relation:

$$R_G = \{(a, b) \mid a \in \mathbb{R}^n, b = f_G(a)\}$$

R_v, f_v define the same for a single node v in G network.⁴

For a single neuron with corresponding function $f_v : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, both can be defined as:

$$f_v(x) = x + 1 \quad \text{and} \quad R_v = \{(a, a + 1) \mid a \in \mathbb{R}\}$$

Thus the encoding for a node with one input is as follows

$$F_v \triangleq v^o = v^{in,1} + 1$$

Models of F_v will be of the form $\{v^{in,1} \mapsto a, v^o \mapsto a + 1\}$ and have one-to-one correspondence with the elements of R_v .

For two inputs: The formula for the encoding of a node with the function $f(x) = x_1 + 1.5x_2$ can be represented as

$$F_v \triangleq v^o = v^{in,1} + 1.5v^{in,2}$$

Generalizing encoding for any single node:

Formalizing the operation f_v of some node v . We assume that the function $f_v : \mathbb{R}^{n_v} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is piecewise linear, i.e., of the form

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} \sum_j c_j^1 x_j + b & \text{if } S_1 \\ \vdots \\ \sum_j c_j^l x_j + b & \text{if } S_l \end{cases}$$

⁴Generally Variables with a subscript G refers to the overall neural network as a graph and those with a subscript v refers to individual nodes or a collection of nodes.

where j ranges from 1 to n_v . This generalizes representations to allow any one linear operation corresponding to some predetermined condition S_i . Each S_i is defined as a formula in LRA over the elements of x . Thus, the encoding for the single node can be written as:

$$F_v \triangleq \bigwedge_{i=1}^l \left[S_i \Rightarrow \left(v^o = \sum_{j=1}^{n_v} c_j^i \cdot v^{\text{in},j} + b^i \right) \right]$$

if statement S_i is *True*, then v^o is equal to the i^{th} equality. The statements are combined together using a conjunction over all possible inputs ($v^{\text{in},j}$) to the node. Each clause joined using the conjunction is in condition \implies assignment form providing the functionality of an **if** statement. So the general way to read this condensed statement is:

if S_1 then ... AND if S_2 then ...

Example (ReLU):

$$\text{relu}(x) = \begin{cases} x & \text{if } x > 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } x \leq 0 \end{cases}$$

The encoding for a simple ReLU function will be:

$$F_v \triangleq \underbrace{(v^{\text{in},1} > 0)}_{x > 0} \Rightarrow v^o = v^{\text{in},1} \wedge \underbrace{(v^{\text{in},1} \leq 0)}_{x \leq 0} \Rightarrow v^o = 0$$

In order to ensure that we are making accurate representations of the actual system that we are modelling, we have to ensure that two qualities are always guaranteed for the encodings: **Soundness** and **Completeness**.

Soundness - This is to make sure that our model does not miss any behaviour of f_v . Let $(\vec{a}, b) \in \mathbb{R}$

$$I = \{v^{\text{in},1} \mapsto a_1, \dots, v^{\text{in},n} \mapsto a_n, v^o \mapsto b\}$$

for any given tuple of \vec{a} and b which is an element of R_v , I is a model of F_v : $I \models F_v$. Soundness is the property of only being able to prove "true" things, any analysis about the system that is proven to be true, will be true.

Completeness - Any model of F_v maps to a behaviour of f_v , so if for a model of F_v :

$$I = \{v^{\text{in},1} \mapsto a_1, \dots, v^{\text{in},n} \mapsto a_n, v^o \mapsto b\}$$

then $(\vec{a}, b) \in \mathbb{R}$. Completeness is the property of being able to prove all true things that can possibly exist in the system. This property can be used to determine *counterexamples* for any given model.

So far we have seen how to encode a singular node in a larger network. But to encode an entire Neural Net, we need to have the following structure:

Encoding the nodes:

for all non-input nodes we have:

$$F_V \triangleq \bigwedge_{v \in V/V_{in}} F_v$$

Since the input nodes do not perform any operations, we are excluding them from the set using V/V_{in} .

the output of v_1 is ... AND the output of v_2 is ...

Encoding the edges:

For some node $v \in V/V_{in}$ there exists a total ordering of edges: $(v_1, v), (v_2, v), \dots$. The total ordering tells us which edge feeds into which corresponding input index of the node.

$$F_{o \rightarrow v} \triangleq \bigwedge_{i=1}^n v^{in,i} = v^o$$

$$F_E = \bigwedge_{v \in V/V_{in}} F_{o \rightarrow v}$$

As per the total ordering of the input edges, $F_{o \rightarrow v}$ determines that the output of the i^{th} node from the previous layer will become the i^{th} input of the present node. The v 's present in the below diagram are the sequentially ordered nodes of the previous layer.

Figure 2.4: Edge Encoding of a Neural Network node

More concretely:

$$v_i^{[o]} \implies v^{[in,i]}$$

The entire network can be represented as a conjunction of the edges and nodes:

$$F_G \triangleq F_V \wedge F_E$$

Assuming that we have ordered input nodes in V_{in} . Let $(a, b) \in R_G$ and let

$$I = \underbrace{\{v_1^o \mapsto a_1, \dots, v_n^o \mapsto a_n\}}_{\text{input}} \cup \underbrace{\{v_{n+1}^o \mapsto a_{n+1}, \dots, v_{n+m}^o \mapsto a_{n+m}\}}_{\text{output}}$$

Then there exists I' such that $I \cup I' \models F_G$.⁵

Example:

Figure 2.5: Generic example with ReLU and linear functions

The functions corresponding to nodes v_3 and v_4 are as follows:

$$f_{v_3}(x) = 2x_1 + x_2 \text{ and } f_{v_4}(x) = \text{relu}(x)$$

The formulations for each of the corresponding nodes will be:

⁵Size of encoding is linear in the size of the Neural Network.

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{Node } v_3 : F_{v_3} &\triangleq v_3^o = 2v_3^{in,1} + v_3^{in,1} \\
\text{Node } v_4 : F_{v_4} &\triangleq (v_4^{in,1} > 0 \implies v_4^o = v_4^{in,1}) \wedge (v_4^{in,1} \leq 0 \implies v_4^o = 0) \\
F_{o \rightarrow v_3} &\triangleq (v_3^{in,1} = v_1^o) \wedge (v_3^{in,2} = v_2^o) \\
F_{o \rightarrow v_4} &\triangleq (v_4^{in,1} = v_3^o)
\end{aligned}$$

Encoding of G : $F_G \triangleq \underbrace{F_{v_3} \wedge F_{v_4}}_{F_V} \wedge \underbrace{F_{o \rightarrow v_3} \wedge F_{o \rightarrow v_4}}_{F_E}$ So far we have been considering the linear operations that form the weights and biases for the nodes in a neural network, however, there are also non-linearities that are present.

How to deal with non-linear activations?

We can create representations of non-linear activation functions by over-approximation of said functions. Over-approximation is the partitioning of the function into different input domains and binding the outputs corresponding to each of these input domains to some defined output domain. For example; we can make an over-approximation for the Sigmoid ($\sigma(x)$) function by dividing the function into appropriate intervals that roughly corresponds to its overall behaviour, i.e., anything less than a certain threshold will give us a 0, anything more than a certain threshold will give us 1 and any input values in between them will give us a value of roughly 0.5.

$$\begin{aligned}
F_v &\triangleq (v^{in,1} \leq -1 \implies 0 \leq v^o \leq 0.26) \wedge \\
&(-1 < v^{in,1} \leq 0 \implies 0.26 < v^o \leq 0.5) \wedge \\
&(0 < v^{in,1} \leq 1 \implies 0.5 < v^o \leq 0.73) \wedge \\
&(v^{in,1} > 1 \implies 0.73 < v^o \leq 1)
\end{aligned}$$

The above can be generalized to any monotonically increasing or decreasing function f_v (which is all activation functions). Assume f_v is monotonically increasing, sample a sequence of real values $c_1 < \dots < c_n$

$$\begin{aligned}
F_v &\triangleq (v^{in,1} \leq c_1 \implies lb < v^o \leq f(c_2)) \\
&\wedge (c_1 < v^{in,1} \leq c_2 \implies f_v(c_1) < v^o \leq f(c_2)) \\
&\vdots \\
&\wedge (c_n < v^{in,1} \implies f_v(c_n) < v^o \leq ub)
\end{aligned}$$

where lb and ub are the 'lower bound' and 'upper bound' respectively. A point to note in the case of over-approximations are that they will give us soundness, but not completeness. Completeness essentially means that our encoding can find **counterexamples**, which we are abandoning in this case. Soundness means being able to prove correctness properties using an encoding, which is of highest priority for our models.

A Concrete Example for checking Robustness

$$f_G : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$$

Where the output vectors in \mathbb{R}^2 correspond to:

$$\begin{bmatrix} p(\text{cat}) \\ p(\text{dog}) \end{bmatrix}$$

Let the specification for this be:

$$\begin{aligned} &\{|x - c| \leq 0.1\} \\ &r \leftarrow f_G(x) \\ &\{r_1 > r_2\} \end{aligned}$$

where c is the original image and x is the perturbed image. The formula generated to check this statement is called a **Verification Condition (VC)**, which if valid then ensures that the correctness property holds.

$$\underbrace{(\text{precondition})}_p \wedge \underbrace{(\text{neural network})}_G \implies \underbrace{(\text{postcondition})}_q$$

inputs: $\{v_1, \dots, v_n\}$ outputs: $\{v_{n+1}, v_{n+2}\}$ Neural Network: F_G

$$\begin{aligned} &\underbrace{\left(\bigwedge_{i=1}^n |x_i - c_i| \leq 0.1\right)}_{\text{precondition}} \wedge \underbrace{F_G}_{\text{network}} \wedge \underbrace{\left(\bigwedge_{i=1}^n x_i = v_i^o\right)}_{\text{network input}} \wedge \underbrace{(r_1 = v_{n+1}^o \wedge r_2 = v_{n+2}^o)}_{\text{network output}} \\ &\implies \underbrace{(r_1 > r_2)}_{\text{postcondition}} \end{aligned}$$

LRA does not support vector operations hence the vector operations are decomposed into their constituent scalars. Absolute value operators are also not available in LRA, so we encode them as: $|x| \leq 5 \xrightarrow{\text{LRA}} (x \leq 5) \wedge (-x \leq 5)$. We need to connect variables of F_G with inputs x and output r .

For multiple Neural Networks, Correctness Properties have the form:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \{P\} \\
r_1 & \leftarrow f_{G_1}(x_1) \\
r_2 & \leftarrow f_{G_2}(x_2) \\
& \vdots \\
r_l & \leftarrow f_{G_l}(x_l) \\
& \{Q\}
\end{aligned}$$

For the above specification we have:

$$\left(P \wedge \bigwedge_{i=1}^l F_i \right) \implies Q$$

For the above F_i corresponds to $r_i \leftarrow f_{G_i}(x_i)$. F_i combines encoding of the neural network F_{G_i} along with connections with inputs and outputs, x_i and r_i , respectively.

$$\begin{aligned}
F_i \triangleq F_{G_i} \wedge \left(\bigwedge_{j=1}^n x_{i,j} = v_i^o \right) \wedge \left(\bigwedge_{j=1}^m r_{i,j} = v_{n+j}^o \right) \\
x_{i,j} \rightarrow v_i^o \rightarrow v_i^{in,1}
\end{aligned}$$

(**soundness**) If F is valid, then the correctness property is true.

(**completeness**) If it is invalid, we know there is a model $I \models \neg F$ if F is encodeable in LRA.

Assuming, input and output variables of the encoding of G_i are v_1, \dots, v_n and v_{n+1}, \dots, v_{n+m} ; each graph G_i has unique nodes and therefore input/output variables.

$$(P \wedge_{i=1}^l F_i) \implies Q$$

The above reads as: "If the precondition is true and we execute all l networks, then the postcondition should be true"

Example:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \{|x - 1| \leq 0.1\} \\
r & \leftarrow f(x) \\
& \{r \geq 1\}
\end{aligned}$$

where $f(x) = x$.

We take the input value x to be equal to 0.99: $x = 0.99$. This is a valid value of x as per the defined precondition.

Therefore, we have: $f(x) \implies f(0.99) = 0.99$ F is invalid as $I \models \neg F$, thus the correctness property does not hold. ⁶

⁶In the formulations that we have gone over, disjunctions arise due to the ReLU function, due to its active/inactive states for all possible inputs to the Neural Network. Disjunctions

2.3.2 DPLL (Davis-Putnam-Logemann-Loveland)

DPLL algorithm checks the satisfiability of Boolean formulae and underlies modern SMT and SAT solver. An extension of DPLL algorithm is needed to handle first-order formulae over different theories.

Conjunctive Normal Form (CNF)

DPLL expects formulae that will be inputted to be in the shape of **Conjunctive Normal Form (CNF)**, all Boolean formulae must be written in CNF as can be seen below

$$\text{CNF: } C_1 \wedge \dots \wedge C_n$$

where each sub-formula C_i is called a **clause** and is for the form

$$l_1 \vee \dots \vee l_{m_i}$$

where each l_i is called a **literal** and is either a variable (p) or its *negation* ($\neg p$). Thus the structure of an entire input should be in the form:

cause problem during solving, as without them LRA (and a similar system called MILP) are polynomial time solvable. To solve LRAs with disjunction we either simplify the formulations by using lightweight techniques to discover whether ReLUs are active or not (abstraction-based verification). Alternatively, we can add additional bias to make all the ReLUs either always active or always inactive. Another thing to consider is that verified NNs in LRA may not really be robust when considering bit-level behaviour.

Figure 2.6: Hierarchical Structure of a CNF formula

DPLL has the following two alternating phases:

Figure 2.7: DPLL Algorithm alternates between Deduction and Search phases

Deduction

Boolean Constant Propagation (BCP) The algorithm searches the Boolean CNF for clauses with single literals, i.e., clauses that contain only one Boolean variable instead of disjunctions of multiple literals. For a model to be satisfiable, the single literal must be True if the variable is p or False if the variable is $\neg p$.

$$(l) \wedge C_2 \wedge \cdots \wedge C_n$$

The BCP phase will look for all unit clauses and replace their literals with True.

Example:

$$F \triangleq (p) \wedge (\neg p \vee r) \wedge (\neg r \vee q)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{BCP: } & (\text{True}) \wedge (\neg \text{True} \vee r) \wedge (\neg r \vee q) \\ & \equiv (r) \wedge (\neg r \vee q) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{BCP: } & (\text{True}) \wedge (\neg \text{True} \vee q) \\ & \equiv q \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{BCP: } (\text{True})$$

Thus F is SAT with the model

$$\{p \mapsto \text{True}, q \mapsto \text{True}, r \mapsto \text{True}\}$$

Deduction + Search

Algorithm 1 DPLL

Data: A formula F in CNF form
Result: $I \models F$ or UNSAT
Boolean Constant Propagation (BCP)
while unit clause (l) in F **do**
 Let $F \text{ b } F[F \mapsto \text{True}]$
 if F is True **then**
 return SAT
 end if
end while
Search
for every possible variable in F **do**
 if DPLL($F[p \mapsto \text{True}]$) is SAT **then**
 return SAT
 end if
 if DPLL($F[p \mapsto \text{False}]$) is SAT **then**
 return SAT
 end if
end for
return UNSAT

The model I that is returned by DPLL when the input is SAT is maintained implicitly in the sequence of assignments to variables (of the form $[l \mapsto \dots]$ and $[p \mapsto \dots]$).

$$F \triangleq (p \vee r) \wedge (\neg p \vee q) \wedge (\neg p \vee \neg r)$$

recursion 1: $F_1 = F[p \mapsto \text{True}] = q \wedge (\neg q \vee \neg r)$
recursion 2: $F_2 = F_1[q \mapsto \text{True}] = (\neg r)$
 $F_3 = F_2[p \mapsto \text{False}] = (\text{True})$

DPLL returns SAT and then implicitly builds the model for F :

$$\{p \mapsto \text{True}, q \mapsto \text{True}, r \mapsto \text{False}\}$$

Partial Model: DPLL can terminate with SAT and without assigning values to each and every variable, these incomplete models are called as partial models. The unfilled variables are essentially don't care variables and can be filled in any way we want. For $F \triangleq p \wedge (q \vee p \vee \neg r) \wedge (p \vee \neg q)$, $I = \{p \mapsto \text{True}\}$ is a partial model.

Figure 2.8: Flow of $DPLL^T$ operations

DPLL Modulo Theories

DPLL modulo theories or $DPLL^T$ are extensions of DPLL over formulae in mathematical theories such as LRA. We essentially treat a formula completely by taking it as a Boolean, then incrementally add more and more theory info to conclusively prove SAT or UNSAT.

$$F \triangleq (x \leq 0 \vee x \leq 10) \wedge (\neg x \leq 0)$$

$$F^B \triangleq (p \vee q) \wedge (\neg p)$$

Algorithm 2 $DPLL^T$

Data: A formula F in CNF form over theory T
Result: $I \models F$ or UNSAT
 Let F^B be the abstraction of F
while true do
 if $DPLL(F^B)$ **is UNSAT then**
 return UNSAT
 end if
 Let I be the model returned by $DPLL(F^B)$
 Assume I is represented as a formula
 if I^T is satisfiable (using a theory solver) **then**
 return SAT and the model returned by theory solver
 else
 Let F^B be $F^B \wedge \neg I$
 end if
end while

$DPLL^T$ Algorithm Constraints are lost in the abstraction process ($F \xrightarrow{B} F^B$) such as the relation between the different inequalities. If F^B is UNSAT, then F is UNSAT, but, if F^B is SAT, it does not imply that F is SAT. The $DPLL^T$ algorithm first uses DPLL to check if F^B is UNSAT following the properties of

Figure 2.9: DPLL^T Algorithm

abstraction. IF F^B is SAT, we will take the model I returned by $DPLL(F^B)$ and map it to the formula I^T in the theory we have abstracted the theory from (LRA in our case). If the theory solver deems I^T satisfiable, F is satisfiable. Otherwise, DPLL^T learns that I^T is not a model so it negates I and conjoins it to F^B . DPLL^T *lazily* learns more and more facts about the formula and refines the abstraction until the algorithm can decide SAT or UNSAT. The whole process is illustrated below:

DPLL takes care of the disjunctions by taking clauses and searching for satisfiability by mapping literals to True or False values. DPLL assumes access to a theory solver to take care of the conjunctions of linear inequalities, in order to check their satisfiability. For LRA, the Simplex Algorithm can be used as a theory solver.

Example:

$$\text{LRA: } (x \geq 10) \wedge ((x < 0) \vee (y \geq 0))$$

$$F^B: p \wedge (q \vee r)$$

$$I_1 = \{p \mapsto \text{True}, q \mapsto \text{True}\}$$

$$p \wedge q : \text{SAT}$$

$$I_1^T = \underbrace{x \geq 10}_p \wedge \underbrace{x < 0}_q : \text{UNSAT}$$

$$F^B \wedge \neg I_1 : p \wedge (q \vee r) \wedge \underbrace{(\neg p \vee \neg q)}_{\neg I_1}$$

$$I_2 = p \wedge \neg q \wedge r$$

$$I_2^T : \{x \mapsto 10, y \mapsto 0\} : \text{SAT}$$

How to convert Boolean formulae into CNF? Usually we use De Morgan's Law (however all are $O(\text{exp})$) What can be used: *Tseitin's Transformation* ($O(n)$)

Tseitin's Transformation

$$F_{x \in S_{\text{var}}} \xrightarrow{\text{Tseitin's Transformation}} F'_{x \in S'_{\text{var}}} \text{ (CNF)}$$

$$S_{\text{var}} \subseteq S'_{\text{var}}$$

Any model of F' is also a model of F , if we disregard the interpretations of newly added variables. If F' is UNSAT, then F is UNSAT, so we just need to invoke DPLL on F' .

Tseitin's transformation changes a formula of computations into a set of instructions, each containing one or two variables, connected by a single unary or binary operator respectively. For example:

```
def f(x, y, z):
    pass
    return x + (2*y + 3)
```

The above function can be decomposed into a set of instructions, that when executed sequentially will provide the same result. For the above example, the function can be decomposed into the following instructions:

```
def f(x,y,z):
    t1 = 2 * y
    t2 = t1 + 3
    t3 = x + t2
    return t3
```

If we are able to conjoin these sequential set of instructions, we will be converting the complex computation in non-CNF to CNF with added temporary variables t_i ; Tseitin's transformation follows a similar procedure over Boolean formulae to generate a CNF.

Tseitin Step 1: NNF Negation Normal Form (NNF) is achieved by pushing negation inwards so that \neg only appears next to variables, e.g., $\neg p \vee \neg r$ instead of $\neg(p \wedge r)$.

$$\neg(F_1 \wedge F_2) = \neg F_1 \vee \neg F_2$$

$$\neg(F_1 \vee F_2) = \neg F_1 \wedge \neg F_2$$

$$\neg\neg F_1 = F_1$$

Tseitin Step 2: Subformula Rewriting Any subformula of F that contains a conjunction/disjunction is called a subformula. We don't consider subformula at literal level.

$$F \triangleq \underbrace{(p \wedge q)}_{F_1} \vee \underbrace{(q \wedge \neg r \wedge s)}_{F_3}$$

$\underbrace{\hspace{10em}}_{F_4}$

F_1, F_2 are the deepest level of nesting, F_2 is subformula of F_3 . And all F_i are subformulae of F_4 .

Assuming F has n subformulae: - For every subformula F_i of F , create a fresh variable t_i . These variables are analogous to the temporary variables that was introduced to decompose some complex program - Starting with the most deeply-rooted subformula: let F_i be of the form $l_i \circ l'_i$, where \circ is \wedge or \vee and l_i, l'_i are literals. One or both of l_i and l'_i may be the new variable t_j denoting a subformula F_j of F_i , create the formula:

$$F'_i \triangleq t_i \Leftrightarrow (l_i \circ l'_i)$$

These formulae are analogous to the assignments to temporary variables in code, where \Leftrightarrow is the logical analogue of variable assignment ($=$).

$$\begin{aligned} F'_1 &\triangleq t_1 \Leftrightarrow (p \wedge q) \\ F'_2 &\triangleq t_2 \Leftrightarrow (q \wedge \neg r) \\ F'_3 &\triangleq t_3 \Leftrightarrow (t_2 \wedge s) \\ F'_4 &\triangleq t_4 \Leftrightarrow (t_1 \vee t_3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} l_1 \Leftrightarrow (l_2 \vee l_3) &\equiv (\neg l_1 \vee l_2 \vee l_3) \wedge (l_1 \vee \neg l_2) \wedge (l_1 \vee \neg l_3) \\ l_1 \Leftrightarrow (l_2 \wedge l_3) &\equiv (\neg l_1 \vee l_2) \wedge (\neg l_1 \vee l_3) \wedge (l_1 \vee \neg l_2 \vee \neg l_3) \end{aligned}$$

$$F' \triangleq t_n \bigwedge_i F'_i$$

each t_i is assigned true iff subformula F'_i evaluates to true. The constant t_n in F' says that F must be true, t_n is like a return statement.

$$F' \triangleq t_n \wedge F'_1 \wedge F'_2 \wedge F'_3 \wedge F'_4$$

2.3.3 Theory Solving

Theory solver for LRA receives F formula as a conjunction of linear inequalities

$$\bigwedge_{i=1}^n \left(\sum_{j=1}^m c_{ij} \cdot x_j \geq b_i \right) \quad \text{where } c_{ij}, b_i \in \mathbb{R}$$

Goal: Check SAT for F and discover $I \models F$.

The Simplex Algorithm will be used as a theory solver, and it expects formulae to be conjunctions of equalities of the form $\sum_i c_i \cdot x_i = o$ and bounds of the form $l_i \leq x_i \leq u_i$, $u_i, l_i \in \mathbb{R} \cup \{\infty, -\infty\}$. The infinities are included to ensure that variables with no upper/lower bounds are also adequately represented.

Converting inequalities into simplex (slack) form:

$$\begin{aligned} F &\triangleq \bigwedge_{i=1}^n \left(\sum_{j=1}^m c_{ij} \cdot x_j \geq b_i \right) \\ s_i &= \sum_{j=1}^m c_{ij} \cdot x_j \quad \text{AND} \quad s_i \geq b_i \end{aligned}$$

where s_i : *Slack Variable* (analogous to tseitin temporary variables)
 Let F_s be the simplex form of some formula F . Then we have the following guarantees (analogue of Tseitin Transformation for non-CNF formulae):
 - Any model of F_s is a model of F , disregarding assignments to slack variables.
 - If F_s is UNSAT, then F is UNSAT.

Simplex Algorithm

Goal: Find a satisfying argument that maximizes some objective function. Our interest in verification is to find any satisfying assignment, so it will be a subset of Simplex.

The set of variables in simplex form is classified into two subsets:

-**Basic Variables:** those that appear on the left hand side of the equality; initially basic variables are the slack variables.

-**Non-Basic Variables:** all other variables.

At the beginning, basic variables: $\{s_1, s_2, s_3\}$ and non-basic: $\{x, y\}$, as Simplex progresses, formulae are rewritten so some basic variables may become non-basic and vice versa.

Simplex simultaneously looks for a model and a proof for unsatisfiability. Each equality defines a halfspace (something that splits \mathbb{R}^2 into two parts). Simplex starts from $I_0 = \{x \mapsto 0, y \mapsto 0\}$ and toggles the values to satisfy all of the equalities. We are total ordering our variables to make it easier to refer to specific variables. We assume variables are of the form x_1, \dots, x_n . Given a basic variable x_i and a non-basic variables x_j , we will use c_{ij} to denote the coefficient of x_j in the equality

$$x_j = \dots + c_{ij} \cdot x_j + \dots$$

for variable x_i , l_i and u_i denotes its lower and upper bound. (Non-Slack variables have no bounds)

Two invariants that are maintained in Simplex: - I always satisfies the equalities, so only bounds may be violated; initially true as all 0 in I . - Bounds of all non-basic variables are satisfied; initially true as they have no bounds.

For $x_i < l_i$, we need to update x_i using any non-basic var x_j . Pick any x_j with $c_{ij} \neq 0$. If no such x_j exists that satisfies our condition \implies UNSAT Increase current interpretation by $\frac{l_i - I(x_i)}{c_{ij}}$, interpretation of x_j increases by $l_i - I(x_i)$, barely satisfying the lower bound, i.e., $I(x_i) = l_i$.

$$\begin{array}{l}
x_j \mapsto 0 \\
x_i = \dots + 0 \dots \\
\therefore I(x_i) = 0 \text{ for previous interpretation}
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{l}
x_j \mapsto \frac{l_i - I(x_i)}{c_{ij}} \\
x_i = \dots + c_{ij} \cdot \frac{l_i - I(x_i)}{c_{ij}} \dots \\
x_i = \dots + l_i - I(x_i) \dots \\
x_i = \dots + l_i + \dots \\
I(x_i) = \underbrace{I(x_i)}_{\text{previous}} + l_i
\end{array}$$

After updating x_j , there is a chance that we might have violated the bounds of x_j so we rewrite the equation such that x_j becomes the basic variable and x_i becomes the non-basic variable. The pivot operation follows as:

$$\begin{aligned}
x_i &= \sum_{k \in N} c_{ik} x_k \\
x_j &= -\frac{x_i}{c_{ij}} + \underbrace{\sum_{k \in N/\{j\}} \frac{c_{ik}}{c_{ij}} x_k}_{\text{replace } x_j \text{ with this}}
\end{aligned}$$

where N is the set of indices of non-basic variables. For Simplex **basic variables are dependent variables and non-basic variables are independent variables.**

Algorithm 3 Simplex

Require: A formula F in Simplex form

Ensure: $I \models F$ or UNSAT

Let I be the interpretation that sets all variables $fv(F)$ to 0

while true do

if $I \models F$ **then**

return I

end if

 Let x_i be the first basic variable s.t. $I(x_i) < l_i$ or $I(x_i) > u_i$

if $I(x_i) < l_i$ **then**

 Let x_j be the first non-basic variable s.t.

$(I(x_j) < u_j$ and $c_{ij} > 0)$ or $(I(x_j) > l_j$ and $c_{ij} < 0)$

if no such x_j exists **then**

return UNSAT

end if

$I(x_i) \leftarrow I(x_i) + \frac{l_i - I(x_i)}{c_{ij}}$

else

 Let x_j be the first non-basic variable s.t.

$(I(x_j) > l_j$ and $c_{ij} > 0)$ or $(I(x_j) < u_j$ and $c_{ij} < 0)$

if no such x_j exists **then**

return UNSAT

end if

$I(x_i) \leftarrow I(x_i) + \frac{u_i - I(x_i)}{c_{ij}}$

end if

 Pivot x_i and x_j

end while

Example:

$$\begin{aligned}x + y &\geq 0 \\-2x + y &\geq 2 \\-10x + y &\geq -5\end{aligned}$$

Converting the set of equations into their slack form:

$$\begin{aligned}s_1 &= x + y \\s_2 &= -2x + y \\s_3 &= -10x + y \\s_1 &\geq 0 \\s_2 &\geq 2 \\s_3 &\geq -5\end{aligned}$$

Ordering x, y, s_1, s_2, s_3 and apply first model:

$$I_0 = \{x \mapsto 0, y \mapsto 0, s_1 \mapsto 0, s_2 \mapsto 0, s_3 \mapsto 0\}$$

s_1 and s_3 are satisfied, s_2 is not: $I_0(s_2) = 0$ but $s_2 \geq 2$.

Modulate the first element in our ordering: x Decrease $I_0(x)$ to -1 to meet s_2 's bounds.

$$I_1 = \{x \mapsto -1, y \mapsto 0, s_1 \mapsto -1, s_2 \mapsto 2, s_3 \mapsto 10\}$$

Now we pivot with unchanged bounds:

$$x = 0.5y - 0.5s_2$$

$$s_1 = 1.5y - 0.5s_2$$

$$s_3 = -4y + 5s_2$$

$I_1(s_1) = -1 < 0$, bound not satisfied.

New ordering of variables: $\underbrace{y, s_2, x, s_1, s_3}_{I(y)}$ value increased by $\frac{1}{1.5} = 2.3$

$$I_2 = \left\{ x \mapsto -\frac{2}{3}, y \mapsto \frac{2}{3}, s_1 \mapsto 0, s_2 \mapsto 2, s_3 \mapsto \frac{7}{3} \right\}$$

At this point we pivot y with s_1

Simplex terminates as $I_2 \models F$.

Simplex terminates due to the fact that the variables are ordered and we always look for the first variables violating bounds (Bland's Rule), this ensures that we never revisit the same set of basic and non-basic variables.⁷

Using Simplex as the theory solver within DPLL^T allows us to solve for LRA, but this approach is not scalable as ReLUs are encoded as disjunctions. This is because the SAT-solving part of DPLL^T will handle it and consider every possible case of disjunction (active = x, inactive = 0), leading to many calls to Simplex, so we extend Simplex to Reluplex [15].

Reluplex

Equations in reluplex form: 1. equations (same as simplex)

2. bounds (same as simplex)

3. ReLU constraints of the form: $x_i = \text{relu}(x_j)$

(also add bound(s) $x_i \geq 0$ implied by relu)

We call simplex on the weaker version (less constrained) formula of F called F' , which does not have any relu constraints. If F' is UNSAT, then F is UNSAT.

$$F \implies F' \text{ (is valid)}$$

If Simplex returns $I \models F'$, it may not be that I satisfies F . If $I \not\models F$, we pick one of the violated relu constraints

$$x_i = \text{relu}(x_j)$$

⁷Basic variables are dependent variables and Non-Basic variables are independent variables.

and modify I to make sure that it is not violated. If any of x_i or x_j are basic, we pivot it with a non-basic variable. The pseudocode for Reluplex Algorithm can be found below:

Note: Without Case Splitting, reluplex might not terminate - it may get stuck in a loop where the Simplex satisfies all bounds but violates a relu, then satisfying that relu causes a bound to be violated and so on.

We try to count whether a relu constraint has not been attempted to be fixed for more than τ times. $x_i = \text{relu}(x_j)$ is split into two cases: $F_1 \triangleq x_j \geq 0 \wedge x_i = x_j$ and $F_2 \triangleq x_j \leq 0 \wedge x_i = 0$. Reluplex is recursively invoked on the two instances of the problem: $F \wedge F_1$ and $F \wedge F_2$.

If any of the instances are SAT, then F is SAT.

$$F \equiv (F \wedge F_1) \vee (F \wedge F_2)$$

2.4 Abstraction Based Verification

Approximate (or Abstract) techniques for verification can have two possible outcomes: - If they succeed, they can produce proofs of correctness for a neural network. - If they fail, we do not know whether the correctness property holds or not.

Abstraction Based Verification techniques require specific techniques in order to abstractly define a domain of inputs to be given to a modified version of a neural network in order to test their robustness. There are mainly three ways of abstracting input domains for verification: *Interval Abstraction*, *Zonotope Domain Abstraction* and *Polyhedra Domain Abstraction*.

Figure 2.10: Different Abstraction Techniques

In **Interval Abstraction** we define an interval for each of the entire set of variables/predicates independently of each other, thereby defining a rectangular structure in some high dimensional space (hyperrectangles).

In **Zonotope Domains** instead of defining hyperrectangles, the input domain is defined as a collection of parallelograms superimposed on each other created using auxiliary variables called generators whose values range from -1 to

Algorithm 4 Reluplex

Data: A formula F in Reluplex form

Result: $I \models F$ or UNSAT

Let I be the interpretation that sets all variables $f_0(F)$ to 0

Let F' be the non-ReLU constraints of F

while true do

Calling Simplex (note that we supply Simplex with a reference to the initial interpretation and it can modify it)

$r \leftarrow \text{Simplex}(F', I)$

if r is UNSAT **then**

return UNSAT

end if

r is an interpretation I

if $I \models F$ **then**

return I

end if

Handle violated ReLU constraint

 Let ReLU constraint $x_i = \text{relu}(x_j)$ be s.t. $I(x_i) \neq \text{relu}(I(x_j))$

if x_i is basic **then**

 pivot x_i with non-basic variable x_k , where $k \neq j$ and $c_{ik} \neq 0$

else if x_j is basic **then**

 pivot x_j with non-basic variable x_k , where $k \neq i$ and $c_{jk} \neq 0$

end if

 Perform one of the following operations:

$I(x_i) \leftarrow \text{relu}(I(x_j))$ **or** $I(x_j) \leftarrow I(x_i)$

Case splitting (ensures termination)

if $u_j > 0$, $l_j < 0$, and $x_i = \text{relu}(x_j)$ considered more than τ times **then**

$r_1 \leftarrow \text{Reluplex}(F \wedge x_j \geq 0 \wedge x_i = x_j)$

$r_2 \leftarrow \text{Reluplex}(F \wedge x_j \leq 0 \wedge x_i = 0)$

if $r_1 = r_2 = \text{UNSAT}$ **then**

return UNSAT

end if

if $r_1 = \text{UNSAT}$ **then**

return r_1

end if

return r_2

end if

end while

1, each generator has its corresponding coefficient values which help in making a convex structure. The main difference between zonotopes and interval domains is that we can encode the relations between multiple variables/predicates using the generators.

In **Polyhedra Domain** we have a setup similar to that of Zonotope Domains, however instead of the generator values ranging from -1 to 1, we have a set of linear inequalities bound together via conjunctions that determine the overall convex shape of the interval we are defining.

These techniques have been described in more detail below:

2.4.1 Neural Interval Abstraction

Using the specifications that have been defined beforehand, we see that it defines a system to test for individual images through a particular neural network.

$$\begin{aligned} &\{|x - c| \leq 0.1\} \\ &\quad r \leftarrow f(x) \\ &\{class(r) = 1\} \end{aligned}$$

There is a great number of possible images x that can be tested for, so we will try to lift the function $f(\dots)$ to work over a set of images instead in order to comprehensively test for possible examples. Thus we want to transform the neural network computation that is represented by f

$$f : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$$

to

$$f^S : \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^n) \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^m)$$

where $\mathcal{P}(S)$ is the power set of set S . Thus, the newly defined mapping from a set of elements (X) to the set of all predictions corresponding to all elements of X will following form:

$$f^S(X) = \{y \mid x \in X, y = f(x)\}$$

where X is a set that is defined as per the specifications as the set of all $x \in X$ that are valid under the precondition. Which for our example will be:

$$X = \{x \mid |x - c| \leq 0.1\}$$

To verify our property, we simply check:

$$f^S(X) \subseteq \{y \mid class(y) = 1\}$$

all runs of f on every image $x \in X$ result in network predicting class 1. We are defining ∞ set of inputs using data structures that we can manipulate called **abstract domains**. So we are taking a Neural Network and generating a version that can take a potentially infinite set of images, however during this

abstraction process we will also be losing some precision, as we will be seeing soon. $f^S(X)$ is called the **concrete transformer** of f .

Example: The function is: $f(x) = x + 1$ Corresponding concrete transformer: $f^S(X) = \{x + 1 \mid x \in X\}$

Interval Abstract Domain considers an interval over \mathbb{R} : $[l, u]$ where $l, u \in \mathbb{R}$ and $l \leq u$

$$\{x \mid l \leq x \leq u\}$$

We simplify concrete transformer by considering only sets which have a nice form (Abstract Interpretation).

$$f^a \left(\underbrace{[l, u]}_{\text{input interval}} \right) = \underbrace{[l + 1, u + 1]}_{\text{output interval}}$$

f^a is the **abstract transformer** of f . Interval $[l, u]$ is infinite (considering $l < u$) so f^a adds 1 to an infinite set of reals. Expanding the above to any arbitrary n^{th} dimension we have a n-dimensional interval (hyperrectangle) region in \mathbb{R}^n , i.e., set of all n-ary vectors $\{\vec{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n \mid l_i \leq x_i \leq u_i\}$

$$\begin{array}{l} \mathbb{R}^n : \text{hyperrectangle interval :} \quad ([l_1, u_1], \dots, [l_i, u_i], \dots, [l_n, u_n]) \\ \uparrow \\ \vdots \\ \mathbb{R}^3 : \text{box interval :} \quad ([l_1, u_1], [l_2, u_2], [l_3, u_3]) \\ \uparrow \\ \mathbb{R}^2 : \text{rectangle interval :} \quad ([l_1, u_1], [l_2, u_2]) \\ \uparrow \\ \mathbb{R} : \text{line interval :} \quad ([l, u]) \end{array}$$

Soundness: We need to ensure that the f^a designed is a sound approximation of f^S . Output of f^a should be a superset of f^S , as we do not want to miss any behaviour. For any interval $[l, u]$, we have: $f^S([l, u]) \subseteq f^a([l, u])$. Equivalently, for any $x \in [l, u]$, we have: $f(x) \in f^a([l, u])$ Although in practice we often see: $f^S([l, u]) \subset f^a([l, u])$

We are modifying the functions to take in intervals of inputs and output the interval that contains the set of all the mappings from the input interval. However, the interval domain cannot capture the relations between different dimensions (non-relational)

$$X = \{(x, x) \mid 0 \leq x \leq 1\}$$

Best we can do is define the unit square between $(0, 0)$ and $(1, 1)$ which is denoted as the 2D interval $([0, 1], [0, 1])$. X defines points where higher x-coordinates correspond to higher y-coordinates. Our abstract abstract domain can only represent rectangles whose faces are parallel to the axes. So instead of capturing the

relation between two dimensions, we are simply saying that any value that is in $[0, 1]$ for x can correspond to any value of y in $[0, 1]$, thereby overapproximating for the function to the extent that we are unable to conserve any information about the relations between the two elements of the input.

Example 1: Consider $f(x, y) = x + y$

$f^S : \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2) \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R})$ is defined as $f^S(X) = \{x + y \mid (x, y) \in X\}$ f^a is defined as a function that takes two intervals (a rectangle) representing range of values for x_1 and x_2

$$f^a([l, u], [l', u']) = [l + l', u + u']$$

$$f^a([1, 5], [100, 200]) = [101, 205]$$

Take any $(x, y) \in ([l, u], [l', u'])$ By definition, $l \leq x \leq u$ and $l' \leq y \leq u'$, so $l + l' \leq x + y \leq u + u'$ thus $x + y \in [l + l', u + u']$ proving soundness.

Example 2: Consider $f(x, y) = x \times y$

For only positive inputs to $f^a : f^a([l, u], [l', u']) = [l \times l', u \times u']$

However,

$$f^a([-1, 1], [-3, -2]) = [3, -2]$$

We were expecting $l \times l' \leq u \times u'$ but we got $l \times l' \geq u \times u'$ which would mean that the result is not a proper interval. Thus we have to compute the interval domain in a different way:

$$f^a([l, u], [l', u']) = [\min(B), \max(B)]$$

where

$$B = \{l \times l', l \times u', u \times l', u \times u'\}$$

For the above numerical example we therefore have: $f^a([-1, 1], [-3, -2]) = [\min(B), \max(B)] = [-3, 3]$

These were all basic abstract transformers that overapproximate for some given binary function.

Affine Function: $f(x_1, \dots, x_n) = \sum_i c_i x_i$ where $c_i \in \mathbb{R}$, we can define the abstract transformer as:

$$f^a([l_1, u_1], \dots, [l_n, u_n]) = \left[\sum_i l'_i, \sum_i u'_i \right]$$

where $l'_i = \min(c_i l_i, c_i u_i)$ and $u'_i = \max(c_i l_i, c_i u_i)$, trying to cover the largest area possible.

Example: $f(x, y) = 3x + 2y$ $f^a([5, 10], [20, 30]) = [3 \times 5 + 2 \times 20, 3 \times 10 + 2 \times 30] = [55, 90]$

Monotonic Function: $f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ $f^a([l, u]) = [f(l), f(u)]$

Example: ReLU in the domain $[3, 5]$ $relu(3) \leq relu(x) \leq relu(5)$ Therefore, $f^a([3, 5]) = [relu(3), relu(5)]$

Composing Abstract Transformers:

For $(f \circ g)(x)$ we do not need to define a different transformer, we can define one for f (f^a) and one for g (g^a) and compose them to find a sound abstract transformer of $f \circ g : f^a \circ g^a$

Example: $g(x) = 3x$, $f(x) = \text{relu}(x)$ and $h(x) = f(g(x))$ Affine followed by ReLU and output in \mathbb{R}

$$h^a([2, 3]) = f^a(g^a([2, 3])) = f^a([6, 9]) = [6, 9]$$

Abstractly Interpreting Neural Networks

For a network $G = (V, E)$
we have: $f_G : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$, where $n = |V^{in}|$ and $m = |V^{out}|$

- f_G^a takes n intervals and outputs m intervals
- for every output node v_i : $\text{out}^a(v_i) = [l_i, u_i]$ (note: we have a fixed ordering of nodes)
- for every non-input node v : $\text{out}^a(v) = f_v^a(\text{out}^a(v_1), \dots, \text{out}^a(v_k))$ where f_v^a is the abstract transformer of f_v and v has incoming edges: $(v_1, v), \dots, (v_k, v)$
- the output of f_G^a is the set of intervals $\text{out}^a(v_1), \dots, \text{out}^a(v_m)$, where v_1, \dots, v_m are output nodes

Example:

$$\begin{aligned} f_{v_3}(x) &= 2x_1 + x_2 \\ f_{v_4}(x) &= \text{relu}(x) \\ f_G^a([0, 1], [2, 3]) &: \end{aligned}$$

Figure 2.11: Example with ReLU and affine functions

$$\begin{aligned} \text{out}^a(v_1) &= [0, 1] \\ \text{out}^a(v_2) &= [2, 3] \\ \text{out}^a(v_3) &= [2 \times 0 + 2, 2 \times 1 + 3] = [2, 5] \\ \text{out}^a(v_4) &= [\text{relu}(2), \text{relu}(5)] \end{aligned}$$

Limitations

Interval Domain often overshoots and computes wildly overapproximated solutions.

Example 1:

Figure 2.12: Grossly over-approximated abstract domain

$$f_{v_3}(x) = -x \quad f_{v_4}(x) = x_1 + x_2$$

So we can see that $f_G(x) = 0$

Expected abstract transformer should be: $f_G^a([l, u]) = [0, 0] \forall l, u \in \mathbb{R}$

But $f_G^a([l, u])$ returns $[-1, 1]$ since it does not know the relation between $-x$ and x .

Example 2:

Figure 2.13: No parameter-parameter relations are preserved

f_{v_2}, f_{v_3} are both relus.

$f_G(x) = (x, x)$ is the desirable result

However, $f_G^a([0, 1]) = ([0, 1], [0, 1])$ is the result.

f_G^a tells us that for inputs between 0 and 1, the neural network can output (x, y) where $0 \leq x, y \leq 1$ which is a loose approximation, we needed $0 \leq x \leq 1$.

We cannot capture set of points where $x = y$ and $0 \leq x \leq 1$, instead we can give $([0, 1], [0, 1])$, syntactically an abstract element in the interval domain is captured by constraints of the form:

$$\bigwedge_i l_i \leq x_i \leq u_i$$

Every inequality involves a single variable and fails to capture relationships so interval domain is called non-relational. To address these limitations we will be turning towards Zonotope-based abstraction methods.

There are multiple methods such as FastLin [39] and CROWN [41] that utilize techniques derived from Abstract Interval to determine an upper and lower bound of a neural network output by propagating bounds through the network layer by layer, from input to output. Both techniques provide overapproximations of output values. However they use more sophisticated methods of generating upper and lower bounds.

2.4.2 Zonotope: Relational Abstract Domain

Assume that we have a set of m real-valued generator variables $\epsilon_1, \dots, \epsilon_m \in [-1, 1]$. A $1D$ zonotope is the set of all points in the set

$$\left\{ c_0 + \sum_{i=1}^m c_i \epsilon_i \mid \epsilon_i \in [-1, 1] \right\}$$

where $c_i \in \mathbb{R}$. For 1 generator variable:

$$\{ c_0 + c_1 \epsilon_1 \mid \epsilon_1 \in [-1, 1] \}$$

This is just defining an interval of the form $[c_0 - c_1, c_0 + c_1]$, assuming $c_1 \geq 0$. In the defined interval, c_0 is the centre. For a one dimensional zonotope this can be interpreted as the point c_0 being stretched in both the available directions with the magnitude of c_1 .

$$c_0 - c_1 \leftarrow c_0 \rightarrow c_0 + c_1$$

Zonotopes are more expressive from \mathbb{R}^2 and above. Thus, similarly for multiple generator variables, we can observe the same "stretching" effect. The initial coordinates are stretched into a line which represents a specific vector with endpoints at $(c_{10} + c_{11}, c_{20} + c_{21})$ and $(c_{10} - c_{11}, c_{20} - c_{21})$. The vector is then stretched by another generator into a parallelogram. The more generator variables there are, the more faces there are in the resulting zonotope. However each zonotope can be described a convex figure resulting from the summation of different parallelograms.

Figure 2.14: Zonotopes built using multiple ϵ_i

The name zonotope is derived from zona meaning 'belt' in Latin. Zonotopes are named such as we can trace an uninterrupted path through the parallel vectors that wrap around the figure like a belt.

Figure 2.15: "Belt" for each Zonotope

In n-dimensions, a zonotope with m-generators is the set of all points

$$\left\{ \left(\underbrace{c_{10} + \sum_{i=1}^m c_{1i}\epsilon_i}_{\text{first dimension}}, \dots, \underbrace{c_{n0} + \sum_{i=1}^m c_{ni}\epsilon_i}_{\text{nth dimension}} \right) \mid \epsilon_i \in [-1, 1] \right\}$$

Example: $(1 + \epsilon_1, 2 + \epsilon_2)$ $(1 + \epsilon_1 + 0\epsilon_2, 2 + 0\epsilon_1 + \epsilon_2)$ Centre will be $(1, 2)$, the centre of the zonotope is always the vector of the constant coefficients.

$(2 + \epsilon_1, 2 + \epsilon_1)$ Two dimensions are equal, so we get a line shape centred at $(2, 2)$. Zonotopes allow us to model relational intervals with the help of the generator variables. Above we see a zonotope modelling an interval that follows (x, x) .

$(2 + \epsilon_1, 3 + \epsilon_1 + \epsilon_2)$ coefficients of ϵ_1 are $(1, 1)$ so it stretches the centre $(2, 3)$ along the $(1, 1)$ vector

Figure 2.16: First step in generating the required zonotope

coefficients of ϵ_2 are $(0, 1)$ so it stretches all points along $(0, 1)$ vector

Figure 2.17: Second step in generating the required zonotope

Above is the final zonotope, adding more and more faces adds more faces to the zonotope.

$$\left\{ \left(\underbrace{c_{10} + \sum_{i=1}^m c_{1i}\epsilon_i}_{\text{first dimension}}, \dots, \underbrace{c_{n0} + \sum_{i=1}^m c_{ni}\epsilon_i}_{\text{nth dimension}} \right) \mid \epsilon_i \in [-1, 1] \right\}$$

We will use a compact notation to signify the above equation, it will be defined as a tuple of vectors of coefficients

$$(\langle c_{10}, \dots, c_{1m} \rangle, \dots, \langle c_{n0}, \dots, c_{nm} \rangle)$$

for an even more compact notation

$$(\langle c_{1i} \rangle_i, \dots, \langle c_{ni} \rangle_i)$$

where i ranges from 0 to m , the number of generators. We can compute the upper bound of the zonotope in the j th dimension by solving the following optimization problem:

$$\begin{aligned} \max \quad & c_{j0} + \sum_{i=1}^m c_{ji}\epsilon_i \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \epsilon_i \in [-1, 1] \end{aligned}$$

which can easily be solved by setting ϵ_i to 1 if $c_{ji} > 0$ and -1 otherwise.

Similarly, we can compute the lower bound of the zonotope in the j -th dimension by minimizing instead of maximizing, solving the optimization problem by setting $\epsilon_i = -1$ if $c_{ji} > 0$ and 0 otherwise.

Example: $(2 + \epsilon_1, 3 + \epsilon_1 + \epsilon_2) \implies (\langle 2, 1, 0 \rangle, \langle 3, 1, 1 \rangle)$

Upper Bound in vertical dimension: $3 + \epsilon_1 + \epsilon_2$; $\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2 = 1 \implies 3 + 1 + 1 = 5$

$f(x, y) = x + y$

Define: f^a

$f^a(\langle c_{10}, \dots, c_{1m} \rangle, \langle c_{20}, \dots, c_{2m} \rangle)$ compare to $f^a([l_1, u_2], [l_2, u_2])$

$$\implies \langle c_{10} + c_{20}, \dots, c_{1m} + c_{2m} \rangle$$

$(0 + \epsilon_1, 1 + \epsilon_2) : f^a(\langle 0, 1, 0 \rangle, \langle 1, 0, 1 \rangle) = \langle 1, 1, 1 \rangle$

output zonotope is the set $\{1 + \epsilon_1 + \epsilon_2 \mid \epsilon_1, \epsilon_2 \in [-1, 1]\}$ which is the interval $[-1, 3]$.

Affine Functions

$$f(x_1, \dots, x_n) = \sum_j a_j x_j$$

where $a_j \in \mathbb{R}$.

$$f^a(\langle c_{1i} \rangle, \dots, \langle c_{ni} \rangle) = \left\langle \sum_j a_j c_{j0}, \dots, \sum_j a_j c_{jm} \right\rangle$$

$$\begin{aligned} f(x, y) = 3x + 2y \quad f^a(\langle 1, 2, 3 \rangle, \langle 0, 1, 1 \rangle) &= \langle f(1, 0), f(2, 1), f(3, 1) \rangle = \langle 3, 8, 11 \rangle \\ 3 + 8\epsilon_1 + 11\epsilon_2 \quad \epsilon_1, \epsilon_2 \in [-1, 1] \end{aligned}$$

Abstract Transformer of Activation Functions

For intervals domains we had: $relu^a([l, u]) = [relu(l), relu(u)]$ This formulation does not know how the inputs are related to their corresponding outputs. Geometrically the interval domain of ReLU approximates the function with a box as shown below:

Figure 2.18: Overapproximations of the ReLU function made using Zonotopes

The breadth of the box depends on the lower bound of the interval, i.e., whether l is positive or negative. Using zonotopes, the ReLU abstract transformer is build using a 1-dimensional zonotope $\langle c_i \rangle_i$ as input

$$relu^a(\langle c_i \rangle_i) = \begin{cases} \langle c_i \rangle_i & \text{for } l \geq 0 \\ \langle 0 \rangle_i & \text{for } u \leq 0 \\ ? & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

If the lower bound is greater than zero, we return the input, if the upper bound is lesser than or equal to zero we return zero. Since zonotopes allows for relating input and output, we can shear the rectangles to form better approximations of ReLU.

Figure 2.19: More accurate approximations of the ReLU function made using Zonotopes

The bottom face of the zonotope is $y = \lambda x$, for some slope λ . The top face is $y = \lambda x + u(1 - \lambda)$. For $\lambda = 0$, we get the base rectangle that is the interval domain for the ReLU, the steepness of the shear depends on the λ parameter, which cannot be more than $u/(u-l)$ to ensure that the parallelogram covers the ReLU along the input range $[l, u]$. The distance between the top and bottom faces of the parallelogram is $u(1 - \lambda)$, Thus the centre of the zonotope is at the point

$$\eta = \frac{u(1 - \lambda)}{2}$$

With this information, we can now complete the definition of $relu^a$ as follows:

$$relu^a(\langle c_i \rangle_i) = \begin{cases} \langle c_i \rangle_i & \text{for } l \geq 0 \\ \langle 0 \rangle_i & \text{for } u \leq 0 \\ \langle \lambda c_1, \dots, \lambda c_m, 0 \rangle + \langle \eta, 0, 0, \dots, \eta \rangle & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

we have added a new generator, ϵ_{m+1} , in order to stretch the parallelogram in the vertical axis; its coefficient is η , which is half the height of the parallelogram. We

also add the input zonotope scaled by λ with coefficient 0 for the new generator to ensure that we capture the relationship between the input and output.

Formal Verification tools AI2 [8] utilizes the improvements made upon the zonotope abstraction to provide guaranteed bounds on network outputs. The input range is represented as a zonotope, after which the abstract elements are propagated through the network layer by layer. Affine transformations are applied directly to the zonotope while overapproximations of ReLU activations are used to calculate output bounds.

2.4.3 Neural Polyhedron Abstraction

So far we have been approximating functions using a hyperrectangle with interval domains but it was non-relational, the zonotope domain allows us to approximate functions using a zonotope, e.g., a parallelogram and capture relations between different dimensions. The **polyhedron domain** is a more expressive abstract domain as it enables us to approximate functions using any arbitrary complex polyhedra. A **polyhedron** in \mathbb{R}^n is a region made of straight faces. Convex polyhedra are shapes that have any two points of the shape completely contained in the shape and can be specified as a set of linear inequalities. This approximation is more precise for ReLU functions than those afforded by the interval and zonotope domains as the shapes used to approximated are not limited to hyperrectangle or parallelograms.

interval domain	\rightarrow	zonotope abstract domain	\rightarrow	polyhedra abstract domain
abstracts a function using a hyperrectangle		approximates a function using zonotopes/parallelograms		approximates a function using arbitrary convex polyhedra

Polyhedra are defined in a manner analogous to a zonotope abstractions, using a set of m generator variables, $\epsilon_1, \dots, \epsilon_m$ which are then bounded by a set of linear inequalities instead of being limited to the interval $[-1, 1]$ as is the case for zonotopes.

A zonotope in \mathbb{R}^n

$$\left\{ \left(c_{10} + \sum_{i=1}^m c_{1i}\epsilon_i, \dots, c_{n0} + \sum_{i=1}^m c_{ni}\epsilon_i \right) \mid F(\epsilon_1, \dots, \epsilon_m) \right\}$$

where $F(\epsilon_1, \dots, \epsilon_m)$ is a Boolean statement that evaluates to *true* iff all of its arguments are in $[-1, 1]$. For a polyhedron F is defined as a set (conjunction) of linear inequalities over the generator variables, e.g.,

$$F(\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2) \equiv 0 \leq \epsilon_1 \leq 5 \wedge \epsilon_1 = \epsilon_2$$

F defines a bounded polyhedron over the generator variables, giving a lower and upper bound for each generator, e.g., $\epsilon_1 \leq 0$ is not allowed, because it does not enforce a lower bound on ϵ_1 . In the 1-dimension, a polyhedron is simply an bounded interval.

To find the upper and lower bounds of a polyhedron, we need to solve a linear program which takes polynomial time in the number of variables and constraints.

To compute the lower bound of the j -th dimension, we solve for the following:

$$\min c_{j0} + \sum_{i=1}^m c_{ij}\epsilon_i$$

Similarly to calculate the upper bound of j -th dimension, we just take the max instead of minimizing the generator terms.

A given polyhedra in \mathbb{R}^n

$$\left\{ \left(c_{10} + \sum_{i=1}^m c_{1i}\epsilon_i, \dots, c_{n0} + \sum_{i=1}^m c_{ni}\epsilon_i \right) \mid F(\epsilon_1, \dots, \epsilon_m) \right\}$$

will be abbreviated as:

$$\langle \langle c_{1i} \rangle_i, \dots, \langle c_{ni} \rangle_i, F \rangle$$

Example: Given polyhedron: $\{(\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2) \mid F(\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2)\}$

$$F \equiv (0 \leq \epsilon_1 \leq 1) \wedge (\epsilon_2 \leq \epsilon_1) \wedge (\epsilon_2 \geq 0)$$

From the Boolean function we can understand that a bounded x-y space is being defined. For ease of visualisation, we can replace ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 with x and y which gives us a set pf equations that x and y must satisfy:

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &\leq x \leq 1 \\ y &\leq x \\ y &\geq 0 \end{aligned}$$

This set of equations clearly defines a LP problem in the shape of a triangle situated in the first quadrant of the x-y plane. Thus the polyhedron comprises of all of the points inside this triangle.

$$\langle \langle 0, 1, 0 \rangle, \langle 0, 0, 1 \rangle, F \rangle$$

We need to solve for the following four equations to get the upper and lower bound on the generators

$$\begin{array}{llll} \max \epsilon_1 & \min \epsilon_1 & \max \epsilon_2 & \min \epsilon_2 \\ \text{s.t. } F & \text{s.t. } F & \text{s.t. } F & \text{s.t. } F \end{array}$$

Thus the valid interval domains of the generators are: $\epsilon_1 \in [0, 1]$ and $\epsilon_2 \in [0, 1]$.

Abstract Transformers for Polyhedra

Affine Functions For an affine function $f(x_1, \dots, x_n) = \sum_j a_j x_j$ $a_j \in \mathbb{R}$
We will have the following abstract transformer:

$$f^a(\langle c_{1i} \rangle, \langle c_{ni} \rangle, F) = \left\langle \left\langle \sum_j a_j c_{j0}, \dots, \sum_j a_j c_{jm} \right\rangle, F \right\rangle$$

the set of linear equalities does not change between input and output of the function.

Example:

$$f(x, y) = 3x + 2y$$

$$f^a(\langle 1, 2, 3 \rangle, \langle 0, 1, 1 \rangle, F) = (\langle 3, 8, 11 \rangle, F)$$

The abstract transformer for ReLU generated in polyhedron domain:

Figure 2.20: Polyhedral approximation of a ReLU function

$relu^a$ in convex polyhedra

Top face: $y = \frac{u(x-l)}{u-l}$ from the equation of a straight line, where $x_1 = l$, $x_2 = u$ and $y_1 = relu(l)$, $y_2 = relu(u)$.

We need to compute the shaded area which is bounded by $y = 0$ from below, $y = x$ from the right, and $y = \frac{u(x-l)}{u-l}$ from above. We define $relu^a$ as

$$relu^a(\langle c_i \rangle_i, F) = (\langle \underbrace{0, 0, \dots, 0}_m, 1 \rangle, F')$$

where

$$F' \equiv F \wedge \left(\epsilon_{m+1} \leq \frac{u(\langle c_i \rangle - l)}{(u-l)} \right) \wedge (\epsilon_{m+1} \geq 0) \wedge (\epsilon_{m+1} \geq \langle c_i \rangle)$$

- l and u are the lower and upper bounds of the input polyhedron that can be computed using linear programming.
- $\langle c_i \rangle_i$ is being used to denote the full term $c_0 + \sum_{i=1}^m c_i \epsilon_i$.
- And a new generator, ϵ_{m+1} has been added, the new set of constraints F' relates this new generator to the input, effectively defining the shaded region.

Condensing the constraints into two dimensions:

$$relu^a(\langle 0, 1 \rangle, -1 \leq \epsilon_1 \leq 1) = (\langle 0, 0, 1 \rangle, F')$$

where ϵ_1 determines x and ϵ_2 determines y thus,

$$F' \equiv (-1 \leq \epsilon_1 \leq 1) \wedge \left(\epsilon_2 \leq \frac{\epsilon_1 + 1}{2} \right) \wedge (\epsilon_2 \geq 0) \wedge (\epsilon_2 \leq \epsilon_1)$$

Abstractly Interpreting Neural Networks

$$G = (V, E) \quad f_G : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$$

f_G^a : n-dimensional polyhedron \rightarrow m-dimensional polyhedron

$$f_G^a(\langle c_{1j} \rangle, \dots, \langle c_{nj} \rangle, F)$$

- For every input node v_i , we have $out^a(v_i) = (\langle c_{ij} \rangle_j, F)$.
- For every non-input node v we have $out^a(v) = f_v^a(p_1, \dots, p_k, \bigwedge_{i=1}^n F_k)$ where f_v^a is the abstract transformer of f_v , v has incoming edges $(v_1, v), \dots, (v_k, v)$ and $out^a(v_i) = (p_i, F_i)$.
- output of f_G^a is a m -dimensional polyhedron $(p_1, \dots, p_m, \bigwedge_{i=1}^m F_i)$, where v_1, \dots, v_m are the output nodes and $out^a(v_i) = (p_i, F_i)$.

Some abstract transformers for activation functions add new generators, we assume all of them were already in the polyhedron but with coefficients set to 0, they get non-zero coefficients only in the output of activation functions.

Polyhedron abstraction is the most expressive technique that can be used to approximate input and output bounds. Consequently there have been multiple tools made using this approach of approximations. One such tool is ImageStars [34] which uses a seed image and generator to model adversarial perturbations in a set. There are also the DeepPoly [30] and GPUPoly [22] tools that utilize different variations of the Polyhedron abstraction for activation functions along with additional interval abstractions to accelerate the runtime.

2.4.4 Abstract Interpretation based Verification

For verification using the Hoare triplet to work, we require the a sound representation of the set of val of x in the abstract domain. Along with the abstract representation of the neural network f on all values of x that results in an over-approximation of the values of x . We also need to check that all values of r satisfy the postcondition.

The generic precondition can be defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} & \{ \|x - c\|_p \leq \epsilon \} \\ & \quad r \leftarrow f(x) \\ & \{ \text{class}(r) = y \} \end{aligned}$$

Here for the sake of generality, we do not specify a particular norm, instead we define an l_p -norm. The main norms that we will be considering in this case are

the l_2 -norm and the l_∞ -norm both of which are distance metrics but serve very different purposes.

$$l_p \text{ norm: } \|z\|_p \begin{cases} l_2 \text{ norm: } \|z\|_2 = \sqrt{\sum_i |z_i|^2} \\ l_\infty \text{ norm: } \|z\|_\infty = \max_i |z_i| \end{cases}$$

l_2 -norm is the length of the straight line between two images in \mathbb{R}^n and l_∞ -norm is the largest discrepancy between two corresponding pixels. They have their own usability based on what kinds of deviations we wish to categorize. If there is a great deal of variability restricted to some locality of the image we can use l_2 -norm as it allows a small number of pixels to significantly differ in brightness. If the noise is random and spread out through the entire image, l_∞ -norm is more suitable as it bounds the maximum discrepancy a corresponding pixels in the two images can have.

Abstracting the Precondition

We have the precondition as: $\{x \mid \|x - c\|_\infty \leq \epsilon\}$

Interval: $I = ([c_1 - \epsilon, c_1 + \epsilon], \dots, [c_n - \epsilon, c_n + \epsilon])$ $\|\cdot\|_\infty$ allows us to take elements of c and change it by ϵ independently of other dimensions. Define abstract transformer $f^a(I) = ([l_1, u_1], [l_2, u_2], \dots, [l_m, u_m])$

$I' = ([l_1, u_1], [l_2, u_2], \dots, [l_m, u_m])$ represents all possible values of r and more.

We have to prove that $\forall r \in I', \text{class}(r) = y$ We see that if $l_y > u_i \ \forall i \neq y$ then, $\forall r \in I', \text{class}(r) = y$

If y -th interval is larger than all others, then we know that the classification is always y .

Note: if $l_y \leq u_i$ for some $i \neq y$, then we cannot disprove this property, so this is a one-sided check. In simpler words, since we will be receiving a range of probabilities corresponding to each of the class indices. We will be choosing the class whose lower bound probability (l_y) is higher than all other upper bounds of all other class (u_i). We will be picking the non-overlapping bound with highest lower bound. If there is any overlap between the range of probabilities, we cannot be entirely sure as to which class the resulting probability belongs to inside of the overlapping region. Thus making this is a one-sided check.

Figure 2.21: An Abstract Transformer returns a range of probabilities corresponding to each class and takes as input a range within which each pixel value will be constrained

Example:

$$f^a(I) = I' = ([0.1, 0.2], [0.3, 0.4]) \quad \text{class}(r) = 2 \quad \forall r \in I'$$

where $I' = ([0.1, 0.2], [0.15, 0.4])$

two intervals overlap in the 0.15 to 0.2 region, this means that we cannot conclusively say that $\text{class}(r) = 2 \quad \forall r \in I'$, so verification fails. $\exists r \in I'$ that can belong to both $[0.1, 0.2]$ and $[0.15, 0.4]$.

Verifying Robustness with Zonotopes

Checking l_∞ robustness property using zonotopes. Since precondition is hyper-rectangular it can be precisely represented:

$$f^a(z) = z'$$

we want to ensure that the dimension y is greater than all others, problem is akin to checking if a 1-D zonotope is always ≥ 0 .

$$z' = (\langle c_{1i} \rangle, \dots, \langle c_{mi} \rangle)$$

To check that dimension y is greater than dimension j , we check if the lower bound of the 1D zonotope $\langle c_{yi} \rangle - \langle c_{ji} \rangle$ is ≥ 0 or not

Example: $z' = (2 + \epsilon_1, 4 + \epsilon_1 + \epsilon_2)$ For this region, we can graphically see that $y > x$ for any point (x, y) To check $y > x$ mechanically, we subtract the x -dimension from the y -dimension.

$$(4 + \epsilon_1 + \epsilon_2) - (2 + \epsilon_1) = 2 + \epsilon_2$$

The resulting 1D zonotope $(2 + \epsilon_1)$ denotes the interval $[1, 3]$ which is greater than zero.

So, for multiple m -generators and n -dimensions

$$(\langle c_0 + c_1\epsilon_1 + \dots + c_m\epsilon_m \rangle_1, \langle c_0 + c_1\epsilon_1 + \dots + c_m\epsilon_m \rangle_2, \dots, \langle c_0 + c_1\epsilon_1 + \dots + c_m\epsilon_m \rangle_n)$$

for some y -dimension check $\langle c_y \rangle_y - \langle c_i \rangle_i$ for every $i \neq y$ and check whether > 0 (we will be getting a set of ranges, if every range ≥ 0 then y is the class)

Verifying Robustness with Polyhedra Analogous to zonotopes but requires invoking a linear program solver.

We represent the interval as a hyperrectangle polyhedron Y . Then we evaluate $f^a(Y)$ resulting in a polyhedron

$$Y' = (\langle c_{1i} \rangle, \dots, \langle c_{mi} \rangle, F)$$

To check if dimension y is greater than dimension j , we ask a linear program-solver if the following constraints are satisfiable

$$F \wedge \langle c_{yi} \rangle > \langle c_{ji} \rangle$$

Robustness in l_2 -norm $\{x \mid \|x - c\|_2 \leq \epsilon\}$: this defines a unit circle around $(0, 0)$.

let $c = (0), \epsilon = 1$

Cannot be precisely represented in the interval domain, best we can do is $([-1, 1], [-1, 1])$ with polyhedra, we can define polyhedra with more and more faces to more accurately approximate a circle, but there is a precision-scalability trade-off that comes into the picture.

Robustness in NLP Synonyms of words should not confuse Neural Networks. Complete set of synonyms: S_w ; each word is w i -th element of a vector is the i -th token/word embedding of the sentence

Correctness Property:

$$\begin{aligned} &\{x_i \in S_{c_i} \forall i\} \\ &r \leftarrow f(x) \\ &\{class(r) = y\} \end{aligned}$$

all vectors x that are like c but where some words are replaced by synonyms. Set of possible vectors x is finite but exponential in length of input sentences

$$([\min S_{c_1}, \max S_{c_1}], \dots, [\min S_{c_n}, \max S_{c_n}])$$

2.4.5 Abstract Training of Neural Networks

Training Data: $\{(x_1, y_1), \dots, (x_m, y_m)\}$ $x_i \in \mathbb{R}^n$ binary label (classification model): $y_i \in \{0, 1\}$

We assume we have a family of functions represented as a parameterized function: f_θ Where θ is the vector of weights. Search the space of θ and find the best values of θ .

Family of affine functions: $f_\theta(x) = \theta_1 + \theta_2 x_1 + \theta_3 x_2$
 Solve optimization problem: $\arg \min_{\theta} \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \mathbb{K}[f_\theta(x_i) = y_i]$

$$\mathbb{K}[b] \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } b \text{ is True} \\ 0 & \text{if } b \text{ is False} \end{cases}$$

This function is difficult to resolve as Boolean is non-differential so we use MSE:

$$\arg \min_{\theta} \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m (f_\theta(x_i) - y_i)^2$$

family of functions f_θ represented as neural net graph G_θ , where every node v 's function f_v may be parameterized by θ . Formally we solve:

$$\arg \min_{\theta} \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m L(\theta, x_i, y_i)$$

Loss function L can also be represented as a neural network. L is represented as an extension of the graph G_θ by adding a node at the very end that computes the loss function.

$$f_\theta : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

Figure 2.22: Generic Representation of a Network for training

We can construct a graph for the loss function $L(\theta, x, y)$ by adding an input node v_y for the label y and creating a new output node v_L that compares the output of f_θ (the node v_θ) with y .

Figure 2.23: Loss Function for Abstract Training

input node v_y takes in the label y and f_{v_L} encodes the loss function, e.g., MSE

$$\left(\frac{\partial g}{\partial \theta_1}, \dots, \frac{\partial g}{\partial \theta_n} \right) \xrightarrow{\text{for a particular } \theta^0} \left(\frac{\partial g(\theta^0)}{\partial \theta_1}, \dots, \frac{\partial g(\theta^0)}{\partial \theta_n} \right)$$

Algorithm 5 Gradient Descent

Require: $j = 0$, a random value θ , called θ^0
 Set $\theta^{j+1} = \theta^j - \frac{\eta}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \nabla L(\theta^j, x_i, y_i)$
 Set j to $j + 1$
repeat

where η is the parameter constraining the steps of the algorithm ($\eta > 0$). We can have another variation of Gradient Descent that does not calculate the gradient of the loss function over the entire training dataset but 'batches' of the dataset. This variant therefore naturally introduces more randomness into the algorithm and helps in faster convergence.

Algorithm 6 SGD/mini-batch gradient descent

Require: $j = 0$, random value θ (called θ^0)
 Divide the dataset into a random set of k batches: B_1, B_2, \dots, B_k
for i from 1 to k **do**
 Set θ^{j+1} to $\theta^j - \frac{\eta}{m} \sum_{(x,y) \in B_i} \nabla L(\theta^j, x_i, y_i)$
 Set j to $j + 1$
end for
 reiterate

Size of batches k is dependent on how much data can be put into the GPU at any one point.

These optimization algorithms do not provide any robustness to the networks, as we are only minimizing loss over average prediction. Not robust to perturbations, even if they are, abstract interpretation fails to provide a proof

due to its overapproximate nature. So we would like to train neural networks in such a way that they are friendly to abstract interpretation.

Redefining Optimization Objective for Robustness (Robustness Optimization Objective)

For every (x, y) in our dataset, we want the neural net to predict y on all images z such that $\|x - z\|_\infty \leq \epsilon$. This set can be characterized as

$$R(x) = \{z \mid \|x - z\|_\infty \leq \epsilon\}$$

New Optimization Objective

$$\arg \min_{\theta} \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \max_{z \in R(x_i)} L(\theta, x_i, y_i)$$

Instead of minimizing for the loss of (x_i, y_i) , we minimize loss for the worst-case perturbation of x_i from the set $R(x_i)$. This is known as robust optimization problem. Training the neural net using such an objective is known as adversarial training (very similar in appearance to minimax or other game playing techniques).

Solving Robust Optimization via Abstract Interpretation

$R(x)$ can be defined in interval domain precisely as it represents a set of images within an l_∞ bound. We can overapproximate the inner maximization by abstractly interpreting L on the entire set $R(x_i)$. By virtue of the soundness of the abstract transformer L^a , we know:

$$\left(\max_{z \in R(x_i)} L(\theta, x_i, y_i) \right) \leq u$$

where $L^a(\theta, R(x_i), y_i) = [l, u]$ Therefore we can overapproximate the inner maximization by abstractly interpreting the loss function on the set $R(x_i)$ and taking the upper bound.

Thus the robust optimization objective can be rewritten as:

$$\arg \min_{\theta} \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \text{upper bound of } L^a(\theta, R(x_i), y_i)$$

instead of treating L^a as an abstract transformer, we can treat it as a function taking a vector of inputs and returning upper and lower bounds, this is called flattening the abstract transformer.

Example: $relu(x) = \max(0, x)$

We have the corresponding transformer: $relu^a([l, u]) = [\max(0, l), \max(0, u)]$.

Flattening the $relu^a$ to $relu^{af} : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$

$relu^a([l, u]) = (max(0, l), max(0, u))$: returns a tuple of values instead of an interval.

$$\arg \min_{\theta} \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m L_u^{af}(\theta, l_{i1}, u_{i1}, \dots, l_{in}, u_{in}, y_i)$$

Where L_u^{af} is the only upper bound of L^{af} output

$$R(x_i) = ([l_{i1}, u_{i1}], \dots, [l_{in}, u_{in}])$$

SGD can optimize for such objectives because all of the abstract transformers of the interval domain that are of interest for neural nets are differentiable almost everywhere. Some can be adapted into zonotopes also.

Example: $f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$

$$\begin{aligned} f^a : \quad & \text{1D zonotope with m-generators} \quad \rightarrow \quad \text{1D zonotope with m-generators} \\ & \langle c_0, c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4, c_5, \dots, c_m \rangle \quad \quad \langle c'_0, c'_1, c'_2, c'_3, c'_4, c'_5, \dots, c'_m \rangle \\ f^{af} : \quad & \mathbb{R}^{m+1} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{m+1} \end{aligned}$$

Flattening does not work for polyhedra domain, because it invokes a black-box linear programming solver for activation functions which is not differentiable.

Neural Networks trained with abstract interpretation are:

- more robust to perturbation attacks
- verifiably robust using abstract interpretation

A Neural Network could satisfy a correctness property but we may not be able to verify the neural net using abstract domain. By incorporating abstract interpretation right into the training we guide SGD towards neural nets that are more amenable to verification.

Note: l_p robustness properties are closely related to the notion of Lipschitz continuity. For instance, a network $f : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$ is K-Lipschitz under the l_2 -norm if

$$\|f(x) - f(y)\|_2 \leq K \|x - y\|_2$$

The smallest K satisfying the above is called the Lipschitz constant of f . If we can bound K, then we can prove l_2 -robustness of f .

2.5 Testing Neural Networks

Verification and Validation methodologies for Neural Networks are often too computationally intensive for larger networks. Their drawbacks include the constant trade-off that needs to be made in-between the precision of the technique and overall scalability. There are other considerations that must also

be taken into account such as the specificity of verification techniques to certain architectures. A verification technique identified for one particular network architecture often cannot be adapted directly without changes to another architecture. Thus, the competing standards for the verification of end-to-end verification of neural networks are often not interoperable, adjustments need to be made on a case-by-case basis. However, so far verification techniques are the only methods to ensure complete and sound guarantees of the robustness in neural networks.

The problem that arises in other methods is the ability to perform search encapsulating the complete input and output spaces. This is caused by the largeness of said spaces. For example, as we have seen before neural networks can be boiled down to simple functional approximators that determine a decision boundary in the input space after transforming through affine and non-linear operations. It is much easier to model the affine transformations in the verification context. However the non-linearities (activation functions) are input dependent and thus give rise to disjunctions that explodes combinatorially due to accumulation of possible states over during the entire forward propagation operation for each neuron. At a glance neural networks are of the following form:

$$f : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$$

As can be seen the input vector is an element of the n -dimensional space which is mathematically an uncountably infinite set. Even considering the physical limit to the precision available for numerical representations to computers and normalized input values, this is a sufficiently large space that makes a brute-force approach intractable. *Input-Output Testing* for a neural network is one of the most reliable ways to test a neural network for corner cases and determine its robustness (heuristically, at least). The corner cases against which neural networks fail are called **adversarial examples**.

Testing criteria like edge or node coverage does not accurately translate to modeling network behaviour [3] like it does in the case for traditional software. Mutation testing is not viable as there is a certain degree of opacity as to how these large networks learn and function. Certain path coverage criteria can be tested but since neural networks are essentially black boxes with very little explainability pertaining to their parameters this does not seem like a fruitful approach. Also, the space of inputs for any fixed path inside a neural network is also sufficiently large along with a high number of possible combinations of paths. Standard mutation testing is also difficult to do due to the low transparency of how neural networks function internally.

2.5.1 Adversarial Testing

Since other methodologies are poorly defined in context of neural networks, the standard testing procedure is the utilization of adversarial techniques in order to find corner cases where the model fails and then include generated examples back into the training set and retraining the model again till it reaches a satisfactory

degree of robustness. Said adversarial techniques (or adversarial attacks) are approximate in nature and may not always converge to a suitable corner case example. Adversarial Testing is the only successful testing paradigm that has been able to generate test cases based on varying degrees of awareness of how a specific neural network functions. The procedure to generate such test cases can be standardized to any specific model irrespective of architecture and is thus the best opportunity to generate test cases where a network might fail.

Adversarial attacks are classified based which portion of the entire system pipeline they target and are generally divided into *Evasion* and *Poisoning* attacks. The general way to remove a bug from a neural network enabled system is introducing the adversarial examples back into the training set with proper labeling so that the network can learn from the same.

Figure 2.24: Current classifications of adversarial attacks

Poisoning Attacks

Poisoning Attacks target the training dataset of any deep learning system. A poisoning attack pollutes the training dataset with training examples that may seem ordinary at first glance but have hidden patterns. This trains the network to misclassify an object when the same pattern is encountered again in the test dataset without affecting the network's overall performance.

This attack is possible since the learning process of neural networks is not parameter efficient. The baseline accuracy, precision and recall of the network is

Figure 2.25: A backdoor classifier is training by introducing a small patch imperceptible to human beings.

not effected, however, a backdoor has been created inside the network causing it to misclassify whenever said pattern is encountered. This is equivalent to having a mini-network trained inside of the larger network that is responsible for learning only the adversarial pattern and predicting a corresponding target class.

The *Lottery Ticket Hypothesis* [7] suggests that within dense neural networks lie there are sub-networks capable of achieving the same level of performance as the original large network after training, but with significantly fewer parameters. These sub-networks are called the *winning tickets* within the network. Therefore it is reasonable to assume that, if true, poisoning attacks install a backdoor in large networks by training a sub-network that learns to look only for a specific pattern in the data (the adversarial patterns that poisons the training dataset). These attacks are often called *Trojan attacks* as they compromise the capabilities of a network by introducing some well-hidden foreign element in the data.

These set of techniques can be useful to model data-shift in the training data and observing how the neural network responds to it. A network that has been trained to be robust can overcome data-shifts if the data pipeline performs data augmentations and transformations capable of removing or distorting adversarial pattern. Techniques like Neural Cleanse [38] can help in determine whether the data pipeline is polluted and single out poisoning attacks.

Evasion Attacks

Evasion attacks are adversarial attacks that perturbs the input data in such a way that it causes the network to misclassify said input. These inputs are generally called adversarial examples. Adversarial examples can be generated to be one of two types:

- **Targeted Examples:** These examples are generally produced to target classification towards a specific category, causing the network to fail in

a very specific way - irrespective of true class the input belongs to, the network will always predict a specific targeted category.

- **Untargeted Examples:** These examples are generated without targeting classification towards any specific prediction category. The aim of these examples is to cause a misclassification irrespective of what the predicted label is, as long as it is not the true label.

Adversarial examples are generally hard to find without any strong constraints. This happens due to the enormity of the input search space. In the visual context, we can take an example image of dimensions: 224×224 . The total number of individual pixels whose values can be modulated in the example image is 50176. The image can therefore be represented as an element in the \mathbb{R}^{50176} space. Brute-force search in such a high dimensional space is computationally intractable, irrespective of the natural limit of the finiteness of numerical representations on a computer. This is because a huge number of the elements in this high-dimensional space do not translate to meaningful images. There are countless variation of static noise, garbled images all which we have to ignore in order to constrict the search space where we can look for test cases. Turns out that the subspace resulting from these constraints is also intractably huge. Thus we need a standard methodology of feasibly generating test cases to test the robustness of the neural networks. This is where Adversarial Example generation techniques come in.

Every adversarial example generation technique will have all four of the following:

- **Seed Data:** Sample data will be used to generate adversarial examples. Adversarial attack generation will search for examples in the neighbourhood of the seed data.
- **Distortion Metrics:** Distortion metrics help in defining the neighbourhood in which a search algorithm will be looking for adversarial examples. This is often the norm distance between the seed image and perturbed image that we are looking at.
- **Optimization Framework:** The framework defines the objective function whose optimal needs to be found. An adversarial example will be found once a local extrema is converged upon.
- **Search Algorithm:** The search algorithm drives the adversarial attack by looking for a viable candidate inside the neighbourhood of the seed data, by perturbing the parameters of the objective function defined in the Optimization framework.

A space of perturbations is described as an l_p norm of the input vector x in a p -dimensional space where each image can be represented as vectors embedded in that space.

Figure 2.26: A norm-ball is defined around the seed image and search is performed for samples in the norm-ball that violate the local decision boundary

Thus the perturbations are constrained to the particular neighbourhood defined by the norm. There are multiple adversarial attack techniques that depend on what information is made available about the neural network model being targeted. A brief description about them followed by examples are as follows:

White-Box Attacks White-Box Attacks are those techniques where all information about the system is transparently available. Thus, a lot of attacks are able to efficiently generate adversarial examples due to the access to gradients which is key in the search process. There are examples such as the L-BFGS attack introduced by Szegedy et al. [3] in 2014 which is prototypical adversarial attack.

Following we the *Fast Gradient Sign Method (FGSM)* was introduced by Goodfellow et al. in 2014 [10]. It works by adding a small perturbation to the input in the direction that maximizes the loss function, calculated using the gradient of the loss with respect to the input:

$$x' = x + \epsilon \text{sign}(\nabla_x l(x, y))$$

$$s.t. x' \in [0, 1]^n$$

The *Basic Iterative Method (BIM)* [17] is an iterative version of the FGSM attack that applies FGSM for a pre-determined k number of times.

$$x'_{i+1} = x'_i + \alpha \text{sign}(\nabla_x l(x'_i, y))$$

$$s.t. x'_0 = 0, x'_{i+1} \in [0, 1]^n, i = 0, \dots, k$$

where α is the parameter that controls the i -th iteration step size and falls in the range $0 < \alpha < \epsilon$.

Black-Box Attacks These attacks do not require any additional information excepting the predicted labels or probability distribution over the k categories. Information relating to gradients is not necessary to generate adversarial examples. A special class of Black-Box Attacks are called *Pixel Attacks* [32]. Pixels

attacks have their distortion metrics over L_0 norm, which determines how many non-zero elements will be there in the perturbation vector. The perturbations therefore have perturbation constrained over the total number of pixels effected. The objective function for the same can be seen below:

$$\begin{aligned} \max_{\delta} f_{adv}(x + \delta) \\ s.t. \|\delta\|_0 \leq d \end{aligned}$$

where L_0 norm refers to the number of non-zero elements in the vector array of perturbations $e(x)$. If want the perturbation over the the whole image to be constrained to only one pixel: $d \leq 1$. Instead of setting a constraint on the strength of accumulated perturbations as is done for different norm distances, we are fixing the number of pixels that can be perturbed but the perturbations can be of any arbitrary strength. The one pixel attack can be imagined as searching for perturbations along a hyperplane parallel to any of the n -axes, when there are n elements of the input vector.

The algorithm used to search in the constrained space as defined by the L_0 norm is solved using the Differential Evolution algorithm.

Adversarial Machine Learning

Adversarial Machine Learning (AML) is concerned with making neural networks robust against deliberate attempts to fool or mislead them and is therefore closely related to testing neural networks. There is significant overlap between AML and Testing of neural networks as AML can help provide tools to test the efficacy of a model. Testing neural networks typically involves checking a model’s performance across different scenarios exhaustively, ensuring it generalizes well to unseen data, and verifying its robustness against unexpected inputs especially when in an adversarial setting. Although testing for adversarial inputs is a small part of the testing process, it is once of the fastest ways to evaluate the robustness of the model. It can help in identifying edge cases and potential failure points. Testing is utilized for not only testing the neural network against potential corner cases but also against standard benchmarks, analyzing its performance metrics, such as accuracy, precision, recall, etc. Testing provides an assessment of how the model generally behaves in practice but does not guarantee correctness across all inputs. A Neural Network cannot be said to be proven correct after testing, it is just an empirical method to determine the standard expected behaviour of a neural network.

There are custom tools like the Adversarial Robustness Toolbox (ART) [23] and CleverHans [24] that can be used to generate adversarial examples based on different adversarial attack techniques. There are several other methodologies that can be used to generate adversarial examples that have not been demonstrated here. However all of these techniques have the same underpinning commonalities that have been mentioned above. Different techniques can be used in different circumstances, as per the requirement and environment under which the adversary is operating. There is also considerations regarding budget that

must be made when generating adversarial examples. Any adversary with an unlimited computational and time budget can generate corner cases that will fool the target network. These conditions must be taken into consideration while generating the required test suite to test a network’s performance in the presence of an adversary.

2.6 Conclusion

In this report we have gone through the two main processes that can be used to award some confidence towards the robustness of a functioning of a neural network. Primarily, we have started with defining the appropriate mathematical models for neural networks to be utilized in the context of verification and testing. This was followed by a set of description of the standard verification process. This include a brief definition of the Hoare triplet that is used to define specifications and the what is entailed in that process. A bifurcation of verification techniques is seen between the two existing approaches: Constraint based and Abstraction based Verification. Under Constraint-based Verification, details regarding the encoding of neural networks has been shared. This includes the encoding of edges and nodes in the mathematical model representing neural networks. Following we have gone over DPLL algorithms and their extensions in the DPLL^T algorithm. An introductory exposition on DPLL solvers is given along with a brief descriptions of Conjunctive Normal Forms (CNFs). The DPLL algorithm was then extended to a larger class of DPLL Modulo Theories to account for Linear Real Algebra (LRA), the theory utilized to model affine transforms in neural networks. A brief description of Tseitin’s Transformation is also given in order to demonstrate the conversion of expressions to CNF. Following which the Simplex algorithm and its extension in neural network context, the Reluplex algorithm is discussed.

This was immediately succeeded by the section on Abstraction-based Verification Techniques. A description of Abstract Interpretation along with a deep dive into the Abstraction methodology of generating output intervals and guarantees. Interval Abstraction was defined and the techniques used therein demonstrated. A more expressive form of interval abstraction called zonotopes were introduced. The process of constructing zonotopes were outlined and the underlying precision vs scalability trade-off was described in detail. The abstraction technique providing more fine-grained control over the approximation intervals is the Polyhedron Abstraction. These is also a precision vs runtime trade-off that must be considered for Polyhedron abstraction. Lastly, a few techniques were described in order to lay the groundwork on the work being done to verify large neural networks.

Abstraction methods along with Precondition abstraction and verifying robustness were described. This was then followed up with Abstract Training and Robust Optimization. These were mentioned to demonstrate that neural networks can be trained with methodologies such that it is provably robust from the very start. The changes that need to be introduced in the loss function,

training process and optimization objectives were all described in detail.

Next, Testing methodologies were defined. Since most testing methodologies would not be implicitly applicable to this use case, Input-Output Testing was described in detail. One of the most important factors while testing with inputs is the rigorous search that needs to be performed in the input space (within some bounds) to look for corner cases that may cause the entire network to fail. This search problem was defined in detail against the context of Adversarial Training. Several techniques and methodologies were outlined. A brief description of Adversarial Machine Learning was given and how it may relate to a part of testing for neural networks.

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